

Agroforestry Policies in France

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Summary

EURAF Policy Briefing #35 is produced jointly by EURAF, and the AgoForAdapt and DigitAF Projects.. The report offers a detailed description of agroforestry policies and practices in France, outlining how the intentional integration of trees with crops or livestock is supported by national frameworks and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Agroforestry is a crucial land use in France, covering approximately 1.55 million hectares. Under the CAP Strategic Plan, these systems are eligible for direct area payments. On arable land, eligibility requires tree density to remain under 100 trees per hectare, while on pastoral land, a more complicated pro-rata system, poses a risk for farmers of losing entitlements if the tree or shrub cover on a parcel is too great.

France utilizes Eco-schemes to reward biodiversity infrastructure financially, such as the "Bonus Haie" for maintaining hedgerows, and the CAP includes performance metrics like committing 3.7 million hectares to climate adaptation. Beyond agricultural subsidies, the briefing explores the intersection of agroforestry with other policy frameworks like the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) regulation and the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR). France leverages the voluntary carbon market through its state-backed "Label Bas-Carbone," providing a methodology for farmers to monetize carbon sequestration from hedges and orchards. France's agroforestry sector is supported by research institutions like INRAE, a structured civil society network, and the "Pacte en faveur de la haie," which aimed at a net gain of 50,000 kilometers of hedges by 2030, but for which funding was severely cut in 2025.

Opportunities include utilizing trees as a climate adaptation strategy to shade livestock and crops, and expanding local bioeconomy supply chains. However, structural barriers hinder wider adoption. The "Statut du Fermage" (Tenant Farming Statute) requires tenant farmers to secure landowner permission to plant trees, effectively blocking investments on rented land. Farmers also face challenges with the complex "Telepac" administrative system, unpredictable budget volatility, a shortage of technical advisors, and an economic "Valley of Death" during the early years of tree establishment. Biological vulnerabilities from pests and land competition from agrivoltaics pose additional threats.

The report concludes with 20 actionable recommendations for policymakers, highlighting the need to reform tenant farming laws, to remove contradictory incentives, to establish a localized "one-stop shop" (guichet unique) to help farmers navigate complex grants, and to secure stable, long-term funding which ensures sustainable maintenance of planted trees.

1 Introduction

EURAF Policy Briefing #35 is jointly produced by the AgoForAdapt and DigitAF projects on behalf of the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), with inputs from other agroforestry projects and workshops organised during the national network Reunir-AF.¹ It has benefited from questionnaire responses submitted during October and November 2025 by almost 140 stakeholders in the French agroforestry sector .

Similar Policy Briefings are being coordinated by EURAF for all Member States in multiple languages on the [Zenodo website](#) of the EU. They will be included in recommendations to be submitted to Member States and the Commission by June 2026 for consideration in draft "National and Regional Partnership Plans".

The Commission's current proposals for the next CAP are outlined in:

- the draft CAP Regulation for 2028-2034 [COM\(2025\)560](#) - which mentions agroforestry in Recital 12 ("The CAP objectives should be pursued through support for investments implemented by farmers and forest holders. Such investments may concern, inter alia, infrastructures related to the development, modernisation or adaptation to climate change of agriculture and forestry, agro-forestry practices, energy and water, installation of digital technologies in agriculture,

¹ <https://reseauhaies.fr/reunir-af-reseau-national-agroforesterie/>.

precision farming, diversification of income sources in other activities such as agro-tourism and bioeconomy")

- the draft National and Regional Partnership (NRP) Regulation for 2028-34- [COM\(2025\)565](#), includes the following definition: "*agricultural area shall be defined in such a way as to comprise only land which is used for agricultural activities, including when it forms agroforestry systems*".

EURAF's current recommendations for agroforestry policy at an EU level are summarised in "*Agricultural Trees for Resilient Landscapes: a vision for European Agroforestry*" ([Feb 2025](#))

This Policy Briefing has the following sections: 1) introduction, 2) definitions of agroforestry, 3) estimates of agroforestry area, 4) legal requirements affecting agroforestry, 5) direct payment rules and TELEPAC, 6) rural development payments and policies, 7) CAP performance metrics, 8) the French LPIS System, 9) stakeholder questionnaire responses, 10) environmental and climate policies, 11) SWOT analysis, 12) recommendations.

2 Definition of Agroforestry in France

Agroforestry is defined by the French Ministry of Agriculture (MinAg 2025) as "*the intentional and integrated association of trees with agricultural crops or animal husbandry on the same parcel of land*". Far from being a novel concept, it is a revival and modernization of ancestral practices that respond to the most pressing challenges of contemporary agriculture (AFAF 2022).² Agroforestry offers a response to climate change, declining biodiversity and financial challenges, and creates complex, multi-strata systems that are inherently more resilient. These benefits are extensive and scientifically documented, including the improvement of soil health and fertility, enhanced water regulation and conservation, natural pest control, diversification of farm income through products like timber and fruit, significant improvements in animal welfare, and the sequestration of atmospheric carbon (PromHaies 2015; Dupraz et al. 2018). An experiment conducted by INRAE in the Hérault department showed that a 100-hectare agroforestry plot could yield as much total biomass as 136 hectares of segregated trees and crops were: representing a productivity gain of 36% (Klorane Botanical Foundation 2019) .⁴

The French [CAP Strategic Plan](#) defines agroforestry as "*systèmes d'utilisation des terres et des pratiques dans lesquels des plantes ligneuses pérennes sont volontairement intégrées à des cultures et/ou des surfaces pâturées sur la même unité de gestion. Les arbres peuvent être isolés, en ligne ou en groupes à l'intérieur de parcelles de cultures (agroforesterie intraparcellaire) ou de prairies (parcours arboré) ou sur les limites entre les parcelles (haies, alignements d'arbres)*".² There is no mention of **tree number thresholds in the definition** but 100 stems/ha is stipulated for silvoarable systems (see Section 5.1).

²land use systems and practices in which woody perennials are deliberately integrated with crops and/or grazed areas on the same management unit. Trees can be isolated, in rows or in groups within crop plots (intra-plot agroforestry) or meadows (parcours arboré) or on the boundaries between plots (hedges, rows of trees)".

The main agroforestry systems in France: hedges or “bocage” in French (above left), concerns more than 50 % of the farms in France, above all in the north-west. Alley cropping (above right), can represent some traditional practices (with fruits trees or poplar), but now developed in modern design with forestry trees. The traditional pastured orchard (Pré-verger in french, below), still represents current practices but the national area has been divided by ten in the last 50 years. (Photos: Agrooof)

In the [French CAP Strategic Plan](#), *agroforesterie* is mentioned 25 times, hedges (*haies*) 163 times, trees 51 times, orchards 92 times, and alley cropping (*intra-parcellaire arbres*) 5 times). The French Ministry of Agriculture announced that the new CAP will be the “CAP of the Hedges”. This is true from the point of view of word-counts. The mentions of *agroforesterie* as:

- a source of carbon sequestration (P19, P29, P86, P193, P198, p201)
- a mechanism to improve soil fertility (p21, p71)
- a "good agricultural and environmental condition" (p71)
- an example of agroecology (p99)
- an effective non-productive investment (p194)
- part of targets for hedgerow establishment (p203) and regeneration (p686)
- a contribution to *zones de régulation écologique* (p224)
- a key part of *terres arables, cultures permanentes, prairies permanentes* (p323)
- an effective productive investment (p816, P824, P851, p908)
- a contribution to multifunctional management of forests (p889)
- a means of adapting to climate change (P970)
- an important contribution to agricultural research (p974).

Ten types of agroforestry are recognised by EURAF (Table 1): dividing land first between "agriculture" and "forest", then classifying agriculture into "arable land", "permanent grassland" and "permanent crops". This classification matches information held in the French Land Parcel Information System (*Registre, Parcellaire Graphique - RPG*) on land-use and crops in parcels and sub-parcels, together with a "*Surfaces non Agricoles*" layer which holds information on woody features like hedges (*haies*), individual trees (*arbres isolés*), lines of trees (*alignements d'arbres*) and groups of trees (*bosquets*). It also locates ponds (*mares*) and ditches (*fossés*). These landscape features must be protected by farmers, BUT they are fully eligible for CAP area payments. The eligibility of silvopastoral or silvoarable parcels containing scattered trees which are not declared as "*Surfaces non Agricoles*" depends on complex calculations explained in Section 5.1

- There are two types of **Silvopastoral systems**: “wood pasture” on agricultural land and “forest grazing” on forest land. As discussed above, France defines “permanent pasture” to include edible shrubs - providing these are not “predominant” in the northern half of France, or even if they are predominant in the southern half (Figure 1).
- There are two types of **Silvoarable systems**: **the most common one is alley cropping**, and a recent one is the food forest - with the latter possible on both agricultural and forest land

- There are three types of **permanent crop agroforestry**: Orchard cropping and Orchard grazing is also a form of agroforestry, together with some specialised uses of fruit trees, chestnuts and oaks³. Vineyard with trees is also another permanent crop system. We can add a fourth, but only on experimental way: alley coppice - with mature trees maintained for timber purposes above short rotation coppice. This remains an agricultural land use in France as long as the rotation length for the coppice is not longer than 20 years and the tree density is between 1000/ha for short rotations and 8,000/ha for very short coppice.
- **Agro-silvo-pasture** is a form of agroforestry where the first part of the rotation is devoted to silvopastoral systems, which is replaced by silvopastoralism when the shade from trees becomes too great.
- **Woody-landscape-features** are hedges, windbreaks of woody strips at the edges of parcels which can have the status of “landscape-features” in CAP legislation - meaning that they must be protected but also that they are guaranteed 100% eligibility for CAP area payments.
- Finally, **urban agroforestry** takes place outside agricultural or forestry land and is not subject to CAP subsidies

Table 1 The EURAF Agroforestry Typology (based on Dupraz et al (2018) and Mosquera-Losada et al (2017))

Tree location	Agroforestry System	Agroforestry Practice	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
Trees inside parcels	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	10 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Alley cropping 3 Food forests	3 Food forests
	Permanent crop agroforestry	4. Alley coppice 5 Orchard cropping, 6 Orchard grazing.	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Agro-silvo-pasture	
Trees between parcels	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Woody-landscape-features	
Trees in settlements	Urban agroforestry	9. Settlement agroforestry	

Permanent grassland (aka permanent pasture) is land used for the production of grass or other herbaceous forage sown or natural) which has not been part of the crop rotation system of the holding for at least five years. However France, like all Member States has the opportunity to define permanent grassland to include grazeable scrub and tree vegetation. In the south of France (Figure 1) permanent pasture need not contain any herbaceous species to be eligible for basic payments as long as shrubs can be grazed "over their entire area" (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #29](#)).

³ Note that areas covered by oak and chestnut trees are also considered as permanent crops if they are grazed by animals within the framework of the established local practices "traditional pig farming system", and even if grass and other herbaceous fodder plants are absent (in the two departments of Corsica); Grazing by sheep and/or goats is also considered as a “local practice” permanent crop in the absence of grass and other herbaceous fodder plants in the Cévennes and southern Causses (heart zone and buffer zone of the Causses-Cévennes site listed in the heritage of the UNESCO and the Protected Designation of Origin area of Pélardon: departments of 12, 30, 34, 48).

Figure 1: Department in southern France where the definition of "permanent pasture" includes grazable trees and/or shrubs even when herbaceous species are not present (Section 4.1.2.4.5 of the French CAP Strategic Plan)⁴

Farmers must maintain their agricultural area in a state that is suitable for grazing or cultivation. This involves different activities on arable land, permanent crops or permanent grassland. Agricultural activities must be carried out annually, except for certain permanent crops, where the maintenance activity can only be carried out every two years.

- **Arable land:** is land regularly plowed or tilled, usually as part of a crop rotation system, including temporary crops, temporary meadows for mowing or pasture, market gardens, and land that is temporarily fallow. It is used for crops that are replanted after each harvest.
- **Permanent crops:** is land used for woody crops, such as fruit and berry trees, vines, and olive trees, that occupy the soil for several consecutive years and do not need to be replanted after each harvest. It includes orchards, vineyards, and olive tree plantations which remain in the same location for a long period (typically more than five years).
- **Permanent grassland.** is land used for several consecutive years to grow herbaceous forage crops for grazing or mowing, which is not included in the crop rotation system, including natural and

⁴Eligible Departments include: **Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes:** Ain (01), Ardèche (07), Drôme (26), Isère (38), Loire (42), Haute-Loire (43), Puy-de-Dôme (63), Rhône (69), Savoie (73), Haute-Savoie (74), **Occitanie:** Ariège (09), Aveyron (12), Gard (30), Haute-Garonne (31), Gers (32), Hérault (34), Lot (46), Lozère (48), Hautes-Pyrénées (65), Pyrénées-Orientales (66), Tarn (81), Tarn-et-Garonne (82); **Nouvelle-Aquitaine:** Dordogne (24), Lot-et-Garonne (47), Pyrénées-Atlantiques (64), Haute-Vienne (87), Corrèze (19), Creuse (23); **Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur:** Alpes-de-Haute-Provence (04), Hautes-Alpes (05), Alpes-Maritimes (06), Bouches-du-Rhône (13), Var (83), Vaucluse (84); **Corsica:** Corse-du-Sud (2A), Haute-Corse (2B). This list of "mountain" and "high-mountain" zones is also used to identify areas eligible for *Indemnité Compensatoire de Handicaps Naturels* in EU Regulation 2021/2115

semi-natural grasslands that are used for grazing livestock or for producing hay or silage. It remains under grass or other forage for a minimum of five years.

In the areas shown in Figure 1, agricultural activity is confirmed by minimum stocking rates and regular mowing or flailing. The required stocking rate is set regionally.

For the maintenance of oak and chestnut forests (CAE/EEC), stocking rate is defined on the basis of the animals covered by established local practices and the oak/chestnut forests of the farm. Failing this, the maintenance for ensuring the production of oak/chestnut trees is required.

3. Areas of Agroforestry in France

Den Herder et al. (2016, 2015) estimated the agroforestry area in France to be around 1,557,000 hectares: primarily from livestock agroforestry systems and wood pasture, and separately reported 598,000 hectares for hedgerows. However, den Herder et al (2025) have recently explored deficiencies of the LUCAS system, and the diverse assumptions which can be made using it. They recommend that future estimates of agroforestry area should be made using the Land Parcel Information System (Registre Parcellaire Geographique - RPG) rather than LUCAS.

A full analysis of tree cover on RPG data will be undertaken for France by the EURAF Project, but Table 5 shows an alternative approach, where all the Corine Agricultural Categories (Feranec et al. 2016), plus natural grassland (3.2.1), is superimposed on Copernicus tree cover density data at 100m resolution. Using this wider definition of "agricultural land" 58.3% of the Corine agricultural pixels have "zero trees": giving France 9th place in the European ranking of "Agricultural Trees Outside the Forest" (ATOF), with **30% of all agricultural land in France having a tree cover of more than 5%** (Table 1).

Table 1: Estimates of the Copernicus 2021 % Tree Cover Density (TCD) on Agricultural Land in EU-27 Countries (all Corine category 2 land plus unimproved grassland - 3.2.1). Arina Machine, unpublished 2025

	Country	0%	1-5%	6-10%	11-20%	21-50%	51-100%
1	Portugal	37.5%	16.9%	9.0%	13.1%	19.4%	4.0%
2	Slovenia	40.0%	10.8%	6.4%	9.5%	19.1%	14.1%
3	Finland	42.5%	12.7%	7.2%	10.4%	18.3%	8.8%
4	Greece	47.4%	10.6%	6.3%	9.7%	19.8%	6.3%
5	Sweden	48.5%	11.5%	6.4%	9.1%	15.8%	8.7%
6	Italy	48.8%	11.4%	6.1%	8.5%	16.5%	8.7%
7	Spain	56.7%	11.5%	6.1%	9.0%	14.9%	1.9%
8	Croatia	58.1%	10.1%	5.3%	7.1%	11.7%	7.8%
9	France	58.3%	12.4%	6.0%	7.5%	10.5%	5.2%
10	Luxembourg	58.9%	12.5%	5.9%	7.4%	10.6%	4.6%
11	Latvia	59.2%	10.8%	5.6%	7.5%	11.6%	5.3%
12	Austria	60.2%	9.9%	5.2%	7.2%	11.8%	5.7%
13	AVERAGE	61.0%	10.5%	5.3%	7.1%	11.3%	4.7%
14	Estonia	61.6%	8.9%	4.8%	6.5%	11.0%	7.2%
15	Belgium	63.0%	10.5%	5.0%	6.1%	9.1%	6.3%
16	Czechia	63.5%	9.7%	5.0%	6.8%	10.4%	4.5%
17	Denmark	63.6%	11.9%	5.5%	6.3%	8.1%	4.6%
18	Slovakia	64.1%	8.6%	4.4%	6.2%	10.4%	6.3%
19	Germany	65.1%	10.2%	5.0%	6.4%	9.3%	4.0%
20	Bulgaria	66.2%	7.9%	4.2%	6.0%	10.0%	5.7%
21	Malta	66.6%	20.8%	6.2%	4.4%	1.9%	0.0%
22	Poland	66.9%	9.5%	4.6%	5.8%	8.8%	4.4%
23	Ireland	68.6%	13.6%	5.3%	5.3%	5.3%	1.9%
24	Lithuania	71.2%	7.8%	3.9%	5.0%	7.8%	4.3%
25	Netherlands	71.5%	9.3%	4.4%	5.3%	6.3%	3.2%
26	Hungary	77.3%	7.1%	3.4%	4.2%	5.6%	2.3%
27	Cyprus	79.8%	7.3%	3.3%	3.7%	4.7%	1.3%
28	Romania	80.6%	4.8%	2.4%	3.3%	5.6%	3.3%

EURAF has suggested using RPG parcel-by-parcel TCD data with a threshold of 5% to identify parcels which can be identified as agroforestry (or with a management plan which aims to excel 5%. The threshold of 5% is recommended since it is used by the FAO to identify "Other Wooded Land" and "Other Land With Tree Cover" in the quinquennial Forest Resource Assessments (FAO 2025) . The distribution of agricultural land

with zero tree cover is shown in Figure 2. These are the areas with the greatest need for tree-planting outside the forest. The index excludes urban areas, mountains and forests.

Figure 2: Tree cover density in France on agricultural land, including Natura 2000 areas, using Copernicus tree cover and Corine agricultural data for 2018. Deep red colours indicate crown covers below 0.05% in each 100m pixel

4. Legal and fiscal issues affecting landscape features and agroforestry

The Loi “*d’orientation pour la souveraineté alimentaire et le renouvellement des générations en agriculture*” (24/3/2025) introduced a new legal status for hedges which replaced many overlapping environmental, urban, and agricultural regulations. Farmers wishing to remove a hedge must now submit a unified declaration (*Guichet Unique*) specifying the strategy for its replacement and improvement. Relocation is only allowed for sanitary, safety, or construction reasons, or for “ecological optimisation”. Article 26 of this regulation also introduces new trial contracts for farmers to enter into land-management “trial partnerships” with others who can bring tree and hedge management expertise.

Agricultural and agroforestry land has a permanent tax⁵ exemption from property tax which was increased from 20% to 30% in 2025/26, but if a farmer plants part of his land as “woodland” (*bois*) it receives a temporary 100% exemption of 10 years for poplar (*peupliers*), 30 years conifers (*résineux*) and 50 years for hardwoods (*feuillus*). The limit of 100 trees/ha is used to demarcate between agroforestry and forestry. For agricultural land in the cadastre (*terres/prés*) there must be less than 100 trees/ha.⁶

Various tax credits are available for planning, planting and maintenance of trees on forest land (*Dispositif d’Encouragement Fiscal à l’Investissement en Forêt*) which are not eligible if the land is classed as agriculture. However agroforestry farmers may be eligible for hedge credits (*Crédit d’Impôt Haies*), or HVE (*Haute Valeur Environnementale*) Level 3 or Organic (*Bio*) certification - in addition to additional “*Bonus Haie*” CAP payments (see Section 5).

⁵ *Taxe Foncière sur les Propriétés Non Bâties* is an annual payment based on the theoretical income (potential rental value - *Valeur Locative Cadastreale*) rather than its actual income or market sale value (to which different taxes apply).

⁶ Exemptions do apply for young farmers - who get a 50% exemption regardless of tree density. An *Exonération Bio* is possible for 100% property tax exemption as long the land is both agricultural and organic.

A tenant farmer planting agroforestry faces three major issues:

- **Right of accession** (*Droit d'accession*). Anything fixed to the ground belongs to the landowner. However the tenant farmer planting trees with permission could be entitled to an *Indemnité au Preneur Sortant* (Outgoing Tenant Compensation) calculated based on the cost of the establishment, depreciated over time, or the added value given to the land. This compensation is not obligatory. And if trees are planted without prior written consent the owner can legally demand that the tenant removes the trees when they leave.
- **Property Tax** (*Taxe Foncière sur les Propriétés Non Bâties - TFPNB*) Even though the owner pays the property tax they are allowed to ask the tenant to reimburse a portion of it, especially if the value of the land changes after planting trees.
- **CAP Area Payments** (*Aide de Base au Revenu pour la Durabilité*). Tenants generally receive CAP Basic Income Support for Sustainability (BISS) payments, and not the land owner. This includes the annual €20/ha "*Bonus Haie*". But if the authorities, using satellite data, decide that there are more than 100 trees per hectare, the parcel may be reclassified as "forest" (although any change is above based on the landowner fiscal declaration) and will no longer be eligible to the CAP grants.

5. Agroforestry in Direct Payments in France

5.1 Calculation of the admissible area for direct payments

Blocks of dense trees over 50 ares (0.5ha) are generally considered to be forest and are not eligible for agricultural area payments. On arable land and permanent crops ("*terres arables & cultures permanentes*") scattered trees of forest species are eligible for area payments up to a limit of 100 trees per hectare. The *Instruction Technique* ([DGPE/SDPAC/2023-408](#)) indicates that all isolated or linear stems of "forest species" must be counted towards the 100 tree limit **even if they are young trees or saplings**. Beyond this density, the parcel with crops is not admissible. Clearly this encourages many farmers to remove "forest species" counting towards the 100 tree limit.⁷

Exemptions are made to the 100 tree rule for a) fruit and nut orchards - which are 100% admissible, regardless of density and b) isolated trees which are officially declared as landscape features (*Surfaces non Agricoles - SNA*), c) hedges which are also declared as landscape features (SNA)⁸ There are also exceptions to the 100 trees/ha rule for a) Chestnut Groves (*châtaigneraies*) if they are managed for fruit production⁹ and b) truffle oaks (*chênes truffiers*) - which are fully eligible for basic payments provided the ground is weeded or harrowed to allow truffle production¹⁰

On "*prairies permanentes*" (permanent pasture) the rules are more complicated. There is no strict "100 trees" cutoff that disqualifies the parcel. Instead, a pro-rata system is used to calculate the "eligible area." This affects mainly the following TELEPAC Codes

⁷ Nut trees include walnut (*noyer*), hazelnut (*noisetier*), almond (*amandier*), chestnut (*chataignier*); Forest species include a long list including oak (*chêne*), beech (*hêtre*), ash (*frêne*), maple (*érable*), poplar (*peuplier*), birch (*bouleau*), and most conifers. but there is a "gray list" of species which may be dual purpose, including wild cherry (*merisier*), service tree (*cormier*) and stone pine (*pin parasol*).

⁸ The SNA layer contains individual trees, rows of trees and isolated trees. Hedges must be less than 20m wide, new agroforestry lines must be marked in TELEPAC using the "hedge tool". Farmers will receive an extra Bonus Haie (20€/ha) if hedges cover at least 6% of both the arable land on a farm and its total utilised area (SAU). The distance between the centres of two parallel hedges is allowed to be 10-40m. If one assumes a 24m spray boom, the centre to centre spacings of rows should be 27-28m to allow the boom to pass without hitting branches.

⁹ In the previous CAP this was TELEPAC code "CAE": *Châtaigneraie entretenue par des porcins ou des petits ruminants* (Chestnut grove grazed by pigs, sheep, or goats). Now farmers are expected to declare all chestnuts as landscape features (surface non agricole - SNA) for full area payment eligibility and use appropriate crop codes like BDH for spring wheat and PPH for permanent pasture.

¹⁰ Similarly the TELEPAC code "CEE": *Chênaie entretenue par des porcins ou des petits ruminants* (Oak grove grazed by pigs, sheep, or goats) has now been replaced by IAE (*Infrastructures Agroécologiques*) or SNA (*Surfaces Non Agricoles*), superimposed on the main crop code.

- **PPH** (*Prairies Permanentes Herbacées*) - permanent herbaceous grasslands on which woody fodder resource is absent or hardly present;
- **SPH** (*Surfaces Pastorales Herbacées*) - herbaceous pastoral areas, where the forage resource includes a few woody species but where grass remains predominant
- **SPL** (*Surfaces Pastorales Ligneuses*) - woody pastoral areas - where the forage resource mainly includes woody resources, and which are considered eligible for area payments only in 38 departments of the South of France.

Non-grazable shrubs, sparse trees, ponds and other features are excluded depending on the area they cover using the following rules:

- 0 – 10% ineligible elements: 100% of the area is eligible for payment.
- 10 – 30% ineligible elements: 80% of the area is eligible.
- 30 – 50% ineligible elements: 60% of the area is eligible.
- 50 – 80% ineligible elements: 35% of the area is eligible.
- 80-100% ineligible elements: 0% of the area is eligible.

The eligibility percentage is decided each year by the managing authority, based on satellite images. The French "Area Monitoring System" (*Système de Suivi des Surfaces en Temps Réel - 3STR*) uses an automated multi-temporal system which "merges microwave, radar, optical imagery, LiDAR and Deep Learning", but is reported to cause and uncertainty and error for farmers with significant areas of trees and shrubs. If farmers get red or yellow flags in the TELEPAC system, accompanied by the message "*Incohérence entre couvert déclaré et couvert détecté (Présence d'éléments ligneux)*" a "mission" will be sent to their smart phones, directing them to specific locations in their fields on specific dates to take "azimuth locked" photos and provide "proof of agriculture" including evidence of grazing and photos showing that agroforestry trees are being actively maintained. Once loaded, the photos will be viewed by human "*instructeur*" at the DDT and a funding decision made.

To be eligible for CAP Payments livestock farmers must also be able to demonstrate that they have at least 0.2 UGB (*Unité de Gros Bétail* - or "Livestock Unit")¹¹ per ha of grazing land.¹² If a farmer does not meet this minimum stocking rate they must prove annual maintenance of grazing land through mowing or mulching.

Eligibility is mapped based on "*Zones de Densité Homogène (ZDH)*" (homogeneous density zones Figure 3), which are homogenous areas with different densities of vegetation (trees, hedges, shrubs...) and/or other non-agricultural natural elements (rocks, stone mounds). The ZDH are digitized in a separate graphic layer integrated into the TELEPAC tool. Some trees and shrubs are considered edible and will be eligible for subsidy, but only if they are accessible for grazing "over their whole surface". In practice this means that the tree/shrub should be no wider than 3 m, and shorter than 1.5 m. A list of "non-fodder" trees/shrubs is given by the Ministry¹³ Oak and chestnut trees can be judged as fodder producing systems, but only in departments in the south of France.

¹¹ Cows and Bulls (1 LSU, cattle 6 months - 2 years) 0.6, cattle under 6 months 0.4, sheep and goats 0.15, horse/pony 1, donkey/mult 0.4, Pigs - breeding sow 0.5, other pigs 0.3, laying hen 0.014, broiler chicken 0.01.

¹² Stocking rates can be as low as 0.05 UGB/ha or 0.1 UGB/ha in areas of Natural Handicap (ICHN - *Indemnités Compensatoires de Handicaps Naturels*) depending on zone (e.g., Mountain, Dry Mountain, High Mountain).

¹³ [Guide d'amissibilité des surfaces](#) (Annex 4), although it includes some traditional fodder shrubs or trees (*Rubus fruticosus*, *Rosa canina*, *Prunus spinosa*, *Ilex aquifolium*).

Figure 3: Extract of the national guide for admissibility calculation (ref). Comparison of 2 zones according to the tree density.

Hedges are fully admissible for area payments if they are 20 m wide and if they don't have any gaps longer than 5 m in length. This second aspect is complicated at a declaration level and farmers may be asked to provide photographic evidence that shrubs or trees do exist in the gaps spotted by satellite.

5.2 Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions for biodiversity and landscape (GAEC)

EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#) summarises the landscape features implemented by all Member States as part of GAEC 2. France has selected all the woody landscape features options: hedges, rows of trees, isolated trees, groups of trees and provides full details of the conversion factors from linear elements to areas and of weighting factors (Table 1). Landowners are obliged to retain hedges. Management and coppicing are authorised provided they are managed after the bird nesting period (16.3 to 15.8) and respect good practices ([BCAE-8 Fiche Technique](#)). If a woody landscape feature is harvested it must be replaced elsewhere on the farm. Intercropped agroforestry areas are eligible if density is up to 100 trees/ha. Short rotation coppice is fully eligible, as are fruit trees and landscape features.

Table 1 Conversions, weightings & protected status for GAEC-8 Landscape Features in France (details)

FRANCE	Convert	Weight	LF	Retention
<i>See section 3.10.3 of French CAP Strategic Plan</i>				
1 Buffer Strips				
2 Cairns				
3 Cultural Features				
- archeological features				
4 Ditches	5	2	y	
5 Field margins and patches etc				
- non productive edges (>1m at edge forest, else >5m)	6	1.5	y	
6 Hedgerows/individual or group of trees/ trees in rows				
6.1 Hedgerows	5	4	y	y
6.2 Trees in Line	5	2	y	y
6.3 groves/copses (max 0.05ha)	1	1.5	y	y
6.4 individual trees	20	1.5	y	
6.5 scrub/ forest margins			y	
7 Land lying Fallow (period of > 6 months from 1/3 to 31/8)	1	1	y	
7.1 Catch crops	1	0.3		

7.2 N-fixing crops	1	1		
8 Others				
9 Small Ponds (max area 0.5 ha)	1	1.5	y	
10 Small Wetlands				
11 Stonewalls	5	5	y	
12 Streams				
13 Terraces				
Notes				
6.1 Linear feature less or equal to max 20m width with trees and other woody plants				
6.2 Tree rows in which the space between rows is less than 5m				
6.3 Non-linear element of trees or shrubs with overlapping crowns less than 0.5ha size				
6.4 A tree separated from a row or group of trees				
6.5 Not used for agricultural production but may be mown or grazed at the end of the year				

5.3 Eco-schemes (Article 31)

The French Écorégime (the national implementation of EU Ecoschemes) is a voluntary payment that replaces the old "Green Payment." Écorégimes comprise 25% of the direct payments or €1,68 Million. It is available for every hectare of a farm, provided that farmers have at least one Basic Payment Entitlement (DPB), or admissible hectare. There are three access paths but a farmer cannot "mix and match" between them. Each path has two ambition levels (Standard and Superior).

- **Path 1: Agricultural Practices** (*La Voie des Pratiques*). This is the most common path for field crops and mixed farms, with eligibility determined by a points system with three criteria: a) **crop diversity** (Arable Land) - where farmers earn points based on the number of crop categories in their rotation (e.g., Winter Cereals, Spring Cereals, Oilseeds, Legumes). Level 1 (Standard): 4 points. Level 2 (Superior): 5 points. Planting 5% of arable land in Legumes (Nitrogen-fixing crops) usually guarantees Level 2. b) **Permanent Grassland Maintenance**: where farmers are penalized if they plow up old pastures - with level 1 being No more than 20% of permanent grassland plowed/re-seeded annually, and level 2: No more than 10% plowed. c) **Ground Cover (Perennial Crops)**: For vineyards and orchards: Level 1: 75% of inter-rows must be grassed/covered, Level 2: 95% of inter-rows must be covered
- **Path 2: Environmental Certification** (*La Voie de la Certification*). This is the "Administrative" path. If a farm holds certain labels, it qualifies automatically without a points check. Level 1 (Standard): CE2+ certification (Environmental Certification Level 2 with a specific focus on biodiversity or fertilizers). Level 2 (Superior): HVE (Haute Valeur Environnementale) Level 3. Special Level: Agriculture Biologique (AB). If 100% of your farm is certified Organic or in conversion, farmers receive a significantly higher premium (approx. €93–€110/ha depending on the 2026 budget)
- **Path 3: Biodiversity Infrastructure** (*La Voie des IAE*). This is the path most relevant for agroforestry. It rewards the presence of "Agro-Ecological Infrastructures" (IAE) like hedges, trees, ponds, and fallow land. Level 1 (Standard): IAE must cover at least 7% of your total farm area (SAU). Level 2 (Superior): IAE must cover at least 10% of your total farm area (SAU). This is based on the equivalent areas in Table 1
- **A hedge bonus** of around €7/ha can be combined with the Agricultural Practices Path and with the Certification Path, but not with the Biodiversity path - since this already awards farmers for their "biodiversity infrastructure". Farmers must demonstrate that their hedges cover both 6%+ of their farm AND 6% of their arable land. They must also qualify for the "Label Haie", and meet the technical conditions in the "Plan de Gestion Durable des Haies (PDGH)".

6 Agroforestry in CAP rural development policies in France

6.1 Agri Environment Climate Measures ENVCLIM (Article 70) (details)

The full list of Agri Environment Climate Measures implemented in France is given in Table 2. Those potentially relevant to agroforestry are marked in bold. Measures 70.06, 70.08 and 70.14 are most relevant.

Table 2 AECM measures implemented in the French CSP (2023-2028) (details)

Article	Code	Measure
Art 70 AECM	70.01	Aid for conversion to organic farming - Hexagone
	70.02	Aid for conversion to organic farming - annual instalments on commitments
	70.03	Support for conversion to organic farming - Corsica
	70.04	Support for conversion to organic farming - overseas departments
	70.05	Organic farming maintenance aid for overseas departments
	70.06	Agri-environmental and climate measures for water quality and quantity management for field crops
	70.07	Agri-environmental and climate measure for water quality and quantity management for perennial crops
	70.08	Agri-environmental and climate change measures for soil quality and protection (Hexagone)
	70.09	Agri-environmental and climate measure for the climate, animal welfare and food self-sufficiency
	70.10	Agri-environmental and climate measures to preserve the agro-ecological balance and biodiversity of specific environments in France.
	70.11	Agri-environmental and climate measure for the creation of cover crops of interest for biodiversity, in particular pollinators in France
	70.12	Agri-environment/climate measure for the preservation of species in hexagonal zones
	70.13	Agri-environmental and climate change measure for maintaining biodiversity by opening up and fire fighting (DFCI)
	70.14	Agri-environment and climate change measure for the sustainable maintenance of agro-ecological infrastructure
	70.15	Agri-environmental and climate measure for banana crops in the French overseas departments
	70.16	Agri-environment/climate measure for sugar cane in the French overseas departments .
	70.17	Agri-environment and climate change measure for market gardening in the French overseas departments
	70.18	Agri-environment/climate measure for specialised orchards in the French overseas departments
	70.19	Agri-environment/climate measures for grassland areas associated with livestock farming in overseas departments
	70.20	Agri-environment and climate measure for the maintenance and environmental performance of small, highly diversified farms in overseas departments
	70.21	Agri-environmental and climate measure for the maintenance and environmental performance of agriculture under forest cover in overseas departments
	70.22	Agri-environmental and climate commitments: "Restoration of the landscape mosaic and fire prevention" - Corsica
	70.23	Agri-environment and climate commitments: 'Preservation and regeneration of ecological corridors favourable to biodiversity on agricultural plots' - Corsica
	70.24	Agri-environmental and climate commitments: 'Soil revitalisation and protection' - Corsica
	70.25	Flat-rate MAEC: 'Protection of water resources - Integrated pest management' - Corsica
	70.26	System for protecting herds against predation.
	70.27	Flat-rate MAEC 'Transition of practices'
	70.29	MAEC API (Improvement of the pollinisation potential of bees)
	70.30	MAEC PRM (Protection of Endangered Breeds)
	70.31	Management commitment - Aid for herd guarding in pastoral areas outside predation zones
	70.32	Agri-environmental and climate change measure - Payments of annual instalments for 5-year commitments

entered into in accordance with the PDR

- **Measure 70.14** will support sustainable hedge management (forestry management specifications) at 0.80 €/linear metre/year over 5 years. A management plan is needed as a condition to get the grant, but is not so demanding as the PGDH (see above). The focus is on "non-productive trees". Hedges should be trimmed on both sides, and cuts made with a chainsaw or a similar tool, making a straight cut similar to a chainsaw (i.e. mowers, flails and circular saws are prohibited). Cutting should be carried out only once every 5 years (except for tree pruning - which can be performed annually), and management should respect the pedo climatic conditions for the production cycle and the priorities defined in the Sustainable Hedge Management Plan (PGDH)
- **Measures 70.06 and 70.08.** Water and soil measures. For non productive trees. From the second year onwards, locate in a relevant way the non-productive elements and surfaces covered by BCAE 8, depending on the initial diagnosis and so as to limit transfers of pesticides and nitrates to rivers and groundwater. In addition, these non-productive elements and surfaces must include: a) at least V percentage points¹⁴ of pollinator-friendly cover from the second year of commitment; b) at least W percentage points of hedges from the 4th year onwards. From the first year of engagement, no inputs on non-productive elements and surfaces are permitted (plant protection products and mineral fertilisers) and no intervention on hedges between the dates defined by the operator (at least between the 1 April and 31 July).

6.2 INVEST (Article 73-74)

Table 3 Investment Measures of interest to agroforestry in the French CAP SP (2023-28)

Art 73/74 Invest	73.01	Productive on-farm investment: support for primary agricultural production and projects by farmers or their groups
	73.02	Non-productive agricultural investments
	73.03	Support for off-farm businesses
	73.04	Preservation and restoration of the natural and forest heritage, including Natura 2000 sites
	73.05	Improvement of basic services and infrastructure in rural areas
	73.06	Infrastructures for defence, forest risk prevention, wood mobilisation and forest forest development in its multifunctional dimension
	73.07	Aid for agricultural water infrastructure in rural areas
	73.08	Productive forestry investments: improvement, productive renewal and global forestry projects
	73.09	Productive on-farm investment - Corsica: support for primary agricultural production and projects carried out by farmers or their groups
	73.10	Non-productive agricultural investment - Corsica
	73.11	Support for the economic activities of rural businesses in Corsica (agri-food and forestry/wood industry)
	73.12	Improvement of basic services and rural, forestry and fire protection infrastructure - Corsica
	73.13	Preservation and restoration of the natural and forest heritage - Corsica
	73.16	Investments to protect farms against predation
73.17	Subsidised investments for young farmers	

- **Measure 73.01 Productive Investments** - can fund material & intangible investments for agroforestry (could be machines or buildings...). Work that may be funded includes: a) perennial plantations, b) Investment with production objectives. Actions that can be funded include: a) plans and studies, parcel diagnostics and territory diagnostics; b) animation associated with the emergence and creation of projects; c) engineering/consulting; d) software, commissioning

¹⁴ Threshold set by operators: V > or = 1 and W > or = 0.2 (200ml hedge for a farm of 100ha)

services; e) investment-related overheads. Funding is normally from 15 to 65% of costs, with the possibility of reaching 80% for agro-environmental projects. Farmers or public/private entities are eligible.

- **Measure 73.02 Non-productive investments** - can fund "material & intangible investments for agroforestry" Work that can be supported include: a) establishment of agro ecological structures, planting sites and maintenance of hedges or trees, the establishment of alley-cropping systems, opening of forest environments, afforestation of agricultural land, ecological corridors; b) parcel redesign (field entry change); c) non-productive agro-environmental equipment for the farm; d) Investments for the preservation or restoration of the environment and biodiversity (species, habitats or landscapes (restoration of stone walls. Actions to be funded include: a) plans and studies, parcel diagnostics and territory diagnostics, b) animation associated with the emergence and creation of projects, c) engineering/consulting; d) software, commissioning services, e) general investment costs; f) implementation of actions necessary for the implementation of territorial policy in favour of bocage, agroforestry' Funding rates are 50 to 100%. Farmers, or public/private entities are eligible.

All the provinces in France have elected the 73.01 measure. But discussions are still in progress above all for the implication of other founding organisms such as water agencies or departments or communities.

	AU R	BRE	BFC	CVL	GE	HDF	IDF	PDL	NOR	NAQ	OCC	SUD
73.02												
73.01												
77.06												
78.01												

6.3 COOP (Article 77) and Knowledge exchange (Article 78)

There are seven types of cooperation projects in France

Art 77 Coope ration, Art 78 Knowl edge	77.1	European Innovation Partnership
	77.2	Encourage organisations, producer groups or inter-professional organisations
	77.3	Cooperation in promotion , marketing, development and certification of quality systems
	77.4	Cooperation for the renewal of generations in agriculture
	77.5	LEADER
	77.6	Other cooperation projects meeting CAP objectives
	77.7	Support for pilot projects and the development of new products, practices, processes and techniques in the French outermost regions
	78.01	Access to training and advice, initiatives to disseminate and exchange knowledge and information

- **Measure 77.06 - Other Cooperation projects meeting CAP objectives.** This include agro-forestry sector development objectives in its list of priorities. Projects must: a) involve at least two entities/actors; b) support for diagnosis and preliminary studies, facilitation and concrete implementation of cooperation; c) specific support for the emergence of possible projects. Costs related to all aspects of cooperation may be covered, including investment costs. The rate is between 50 and 100% over a period of up to 7 years. For investments the maximum rate to be respected. Beneficiaries can be legal or natural persons involved in a partnership between at least two entities.
- **Measure 78.01: Training, counselling, dissemination and access to knowledge.** Building knowledge skills to change practices is the focus, and agroforestry is mentioned. Possible actions include: a)

training; b) strategic and technical advice, individualised or collective, which must promote a global vision of the operation or the farm and the integration of the project in its territory; c) collective dynamics and territorial or thematic animation (awareness of new practices). Aid rate is a maximum of 100%. Beneficiaries can be legal persons, public or private, working in the fields of training, dissemination of knowledge and information and advice or/and legal or natural persons benefiting from counselling services

7 Agroforestry and CAP performance metrics in France

The Results (R), Output (O) and Impact (I) indicators are used by the Commission to measure the achievement of the objectives of the CAP as a whole. The following figures are based on the EU Commission's "At a glance: France's CAP Strategic Plan" (2023-2027) and the standard reference data for France (approx. 28 million ha UAA and 456,000 farms).

- **R.12 Adaptation to climate change:** percentage of UAS subject to subsidised commitments to improve adaptation to climate change. Up to **3.7 million** hectares will be committed to contribute to this result indicator (the organic farming area has not been computed).
- **R.14 Carbon storage in soils and biomass:** percentage of UAS subject to subsidised commitments to reduce emissions, or maintain and improve carbon storage (including permanent grasslands, permanent crops with permanent vegetation cover, and agricultural land in wetlands and peatlands). The general target value for France is **9 million** ha (i.e 32.1% of the UAA).
- **R.16 Climate-related investments:** percentage of agricultural holdings benefiting from CAP investment aid that contribute to adaptation to climate change and its mitigation, as well as to the production of renewable energy or biomaterials. The target value is **2.5%** of farms.
- **R.17 Forested lands:** subsidised area for afforestation, agroforestry and reclamation. The result indicator for France is **400** ha, but largely because new planting in France is now funded outside the CAP. It is intended to plant 1,750 km of hedges / year.
- **R.18 Investment aid for the forestry sector:** total investment to improve the performance of the forestry sector. The objective is **€100** million.
- **R.19 Soil improvement and protection:** percentage of UAAs subject to beneficial aid commitments for soil management aimed at improving soil quality and biota (such as reduced tillage, soil cover with crops and crop rotation, including legumes). The number of hectares planned under these commitments is **3.7 million** ha (**13.5%** of the UAA).
- **R.25 Environmental performance in the livestock sector:** percentage of livestock units subject to subsidised commitments to improve environmental sustainability. The number of livestock units subject to these commitments is **400,000**, which represents 2.13% of the total.
- **R.26 Investments related to natural resources:** percentage of agricultural holdings benefiting from CAP aid for productive and non-productive investments related to the protection of natural resources. The number of farms receiving relevant aid is **14,000**, or **3%** of the total.
- **R.30 Support for sustainable forest management:** area of forest land subject to commitments to support forest protection and management of ecosystem services. The number of hectares under this objective is **44,000** ha.
- **R.31 Preservation of habitats and species:** percentage of UAAs subject to aid commitments that promote the conservation or recovery of biodiversity, including high natural value agricultural practices. The overall target value is **16 million** ha, or **57%** of the UAA. *(Note: This high percentage includes broad eco-schemes and conditionality baseline compliance linked to biodiversity).*
- **R.32 Investments related to biodiversity:** percentage of farms that receive CAP investment aid in favor of biodiversity. The general objective is **1,000** farms (0.22% of the total) that will receive the relevant aid.
- **R.34 Preservation of landscape elements:** percentage of used agricultural area (UAA) subject to subsidised commitments for the management of landscape elements, including hedges and trees. This result can also include the surface of "permanent crops", so it could cover larger areas than those strictly considered "landscape elements", according to the CAP Implementing Regulation. The UAA subject to financed commitments to manage landscape elements is targeted at **70,000** ha.
- **O.14** Number of hectares (excluding forestry) or number of other units subject to environmental or climate commitments that go beyond mandatory requirements. The total planned area is **3.7 million** ha, with a total expenditure allocation of **€5.4 billion**.

- **O.15** Number of hectares (forestry) or number of other units subject to environmental or climate commitments that go beyond mandatory requirements. Management commitments include **44,000** ha (5,000 units), with a financial allocation (total public expenditure of **€60 million**).
- **O.16 Maintenance payments for forestry and agroforestry:** The total planned area is **400** ha with a cost of **€1 million**, but no breakdown is provided between afforestation, restoration and reforestation.

8. Agroforestry in the French LPIS System (RPG)

Agroforestry and land-use codes in the LPIS systems of Member States in the Western region of Europe ([EURAF 2025](#)) show that all countries share difficulties in accurately identifying parcels and parcel boundaries containing trees. The Registre Parcellaire Graphique (RPG) is managed by Agence de Services et de Paiement (ASP) and accessed by farmers via the Telepac interface. It has a high degree of granularity: not merely classifying land cover but allowing for "Precisions" that modify the legal status of the crop code ([Dossier PAC 2024](#)). The three most useful codes for woody crops are:

- **Taillis à Courte Rotation – Code: TCR** This is Short Rotation Coppice on agricultural land. Its rotation length must not exceed 20 years and only 11 species or species groups can be used with some density defined by species.¹⁵ EURAF stresses the value of "Alley Coppice" (Paris et al. 2016) as one of the 8 types of agroforestry on agricultural land (EURAF Policy Briefing #1), with a focus on biomass and protein production in diverse ecosystems. Short rotation coppice is classified as a Permanent Crops and is 100 % eligible for basic income support.
- **Boisement de Terres Agricoles – Code: BTA** - This is agricultural land which was afforested with government assistance, but remains eligible for area payments (*DPB - Droit au Paiement de Base*) for the commitment period of the tree planting scheme - usually 15 years. At the end of this period the parcel will automatically be reclassified as **SBO (Surfaces Boisées)** and lose DPB eligibility. This code is different from **FOR (Forêt)** - which is part of the forest registry and has not been agricultural for a long time. However, if the afforested block is smaller than 50 ares (0.5ha) it might be classified as a landscape element **IAE (Infrastructures Agroécologiques)**¹⁶, and would remain eligible for the CAP area payment. This code should be used for "afforestation" and not "agroforestation"
- **Prairies Permanentes - Codes: PPH** - This is the standard code for permanent grassland. However, silvopastoral areas can be identified through the *Systeme de Pro-rata* (SPR). Remote sensing is used to calculate the density of trees and a "pro-rata" eligibility coefficient. If density is below a certain threshold (e.g., 100 trees/ha), the entire area remains eligible.
- **Surface Pastorale Ligneuse - Code SPL** - is used only in the southern, Mediterranean regions of France, where it explicitly recognizes rangelands where woody vegetation (shrubs, trees) are dominant but where forage is still available. Unlike PPH, which implies a grass-dominant system, SPL acknowledges that the livestock browse the woody component.
- **Precision Codes:** The RPG also expects farmers to add specific flags to crop codes. These are covered by a 50 page "Notice Cultures et Précisions" and include details on: a) Harvest Type (Type de Récolte), b) Species and Varietal Details, c) mixture ratios (Mélanges), d) end destination, e) the "border exception" - showing which parcel code is associated with a border (BOR) or buffer strip (BTA)
- **Surfaces Non Agricoles - SNA Codes** - These codes are used for permanent landscape features which are held in a separate layer on top of the polygons used for primary crops: **HAI:** Haie (Hedgerow) – Must be less than 10 meters wide, **ALI:** Alignement d'arbres (Line of trees), **ISO:** Arbre

¹⁵Aulne glutineux (*Alnus glutinosa*) Bouleau verruqueux (*Betula pendula*) Charme (*Carpinus betulus*) Châtaignier (*Castanea sativa*) Érable sycomore (*Acer pseudoplatanus*) Eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus gunnii* & *Eucalyptus gundal*), Frêne commun (*Fraxinus excelsior*) Merisier (*Prunus avium*) Peupliers - toutes espèces (*Populus sp.*), Robinier faux-acacia (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) Saules - toutes espèces (*Salix spp.*). (Arrêté du 13 mai 2023 - [Légifrance](#)) ... High protein coppicing species like Mûrier blanc (*Morus alba*), Tagasate (*Chamaecytisus palmensis*), Févier d'Amérique (*Gleditsia triacanthos*), L'aulne à feuilles de cœur (*Alnus cordata*) could usefully be added to this list - particularly in view of the upcoming EU Livestock and Protein Strategies.

¹⁶Other IAEs are: **ALI:** Alignement d'arbres (Line of trees), **HAI:** Haies (Hedges), **BOS:** Bosquets (Small groups of trees, (0.01 - 0.5 hectares), **ISO:** Arbres isolés (Isolated trees), **MAR:** Mares (Ponds), **NUR:** Murets (Stone walls), **Bandes tampons:** (Buffer strips along watercourses), **Fiches:** (Fallow land/set-aside)

isolé (Isolated standalone tree), **BOS**: Bosquet (Small wood or grove) – Must be between 0.01 and 0.5 hectares, **MAR**: Mare (Pond) – Must be between 0.01 and 0.5 hectares, **FOS**: Fossé (Ditch) – Earth ditches, non-concreted, maximum 6 meters wide, **MUR**: Mur (Traditional stone wall) – Must be bare stone/dry stone, **TER**: Terrasse (Terrace) – Traditional agricultural terracing.

- **Crop codes which count as IAE (Infrastructures Agroécologiques)**: These are areas of land declared as a primary "crop" for the specific parcel, but because of their ecological nature, the CAP administration counts them toward your IAE biodiversity quotas. **Borders and Strips**: **BOR**: Bordure de champ (Field border), **BTA**: Bande tampon (Buffer strip, usually along watercourses), **BFS**: Bande le long d'une forêt, sans production (Strip along a forest edge, non-productive), **BFP**: Bande le long d'une forêt, avec production (Strip along a forest edge, productive). **Fallow land** (Jachères) **J5M**: Jachère de 5 ans ou moins (Standard fallow land under 5 years), **J6S**: Jachère de 6 ans ou plus déclarée comme IAE (Long-term fallow land specifically kept for ecological focus)

9. Agroforestry Stakeholder Surveys

Over the past 10 years several surveys of farmer attitudes have taken place including those undertaken by the AGFORWARD Project (2014-17), and the Collectif Nourrir/BVA survey (2024):

- The AGFORWARD project conducted workshops in 13 European countries with a standardised questionnaire evaluating 45 different aspects of agroforestry. In France, the respondents were grouped into 4 regional groups (Poitou-Charentes, Picardy, Brittany, Southern France) (Burgess et al. 2018; García de Jalón et al. 2018). The highest-ranked positives for agroforestry were biodiversity and habitat, soil conservation, agro-ecological synergy and originality/synergy. The negatives were: complexity of work, mechanical difficulties, administrative burden and pest/weed control.
- The BVA XSight survey of 600+ representative French farmers was conducted on behalf of Collectif Nourrir, Terra Nova, and Parlons Climat (BVA Xsight - Crise Agricole Sondage). It showed that only 15% of farmers were opposed to the "ecological transition" and that farmers are squeezed by rising production costs, market instability and low sale prices. A majority was willing to plant trees on their farms but were limited by access to funding for establishment and maintenance costs.

During October 2025 the AgroForAdapt project conducted a detailed survey of stakeholders in Spain and France, with 137 responses from France. The findings ([EURAF Research Report #56](#)) reveal that while enthusiasm for agroforestry is high among farmers and technical experts, and its ecological benefits are overwhelmingly recognized, widespread adoption is being actively stifled by severe, interconnected failures in policy, law, and market structures. The data points to three core failures impeding progress:

- First is a **policy and economic failure**, where the French implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its associated administrative systems (like the Land Parcel Information System, TELEPAC) are described as complex, contradictory, and financially insufficient. Farmers and technicians also point out the lack of sustainability of the rules and tools for area declarations. Respondents identify rigid definitions and buggy administrative portals that penalize farmers for planting trees.
- Second is a **legal and land failure**. A structural impasse in French tenancy law (the Code rural) creates a split incentive that makes agroforestry economically irrational for tenant farmers. The law dictates that trees (a long-term asset) become the property of the landowner, even if the tenant bears 100% of the cost and short-term yield loss, effectively blocking investment on rented land, which represents today more than 55 % of the land in France.
- Third is a **cultural and market failure**. Farmers who adopt agroforestry report social mockery from the mainstream agricultural sector, which still largely views trees as obstacles to mechanization. This is compounded by an absence of clear value chains for agroforestry products (e.g., timber, fodder, wood chips), turning tree maintenance into a cost rather than a revenue stream.

Stakeholder feedback identified that the top priorities were not for more information about agroforestry but for functional, profitable, and simple rules. The most urgent technical demands include: 1) removing the official CAP guidance that defines woody landscape features as "non-productive," 2) increasing eco-scheme and investment payments, 3) abandoning the GAEC rules, and 4) Integration of clear silvoarable and silvopastoral land use codes into the TELEPAC (LPIS) system.

10 Agroforestry and Environmental Policies beyond the CAP

10.1 Agroforestry in the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation

The [National Energy and Climate Plan](#) (NECP) confirms that France will miss its 2030 LULUCF net emissions target of -34.046 Mt by a long way. It projects only -18.00 Mt CO₂e by 2030, even with additional measures. Net emissions were -27.343 Mt CO₂e in 2016, but had fallen to -16.92Mt CO₂e in 2022. This worsening trend is projected to continue up to 2050, reflecting a "severe mortality and growth crisis" in the French forestry sector " due to the effects of climate change with increased mortality and reduced growth in forests, due to drought, fires, storms, pests etc..

The NECP therefore indicates that France is implementing an array of public policies to enhance the carbon sink, including: a) Tax incentive Scheme for Investment in Forests, b) Forest and Insurance Investment Account, c) Forest Fire Control System, d) Low-Carbon Label to encourage Carbon-Sequestration schemes (of the 11 methods already approved, 3 include tree planting); e) National Forest and Timber Programme, f) Action Plan for the Recovery of the Forest-based Sector, g) Forest and Woodland Research and Innovation Plan, h) Law to Strengthen Prevention in the Fight Against Forest Fires, i) and major efforts in the agriculture sector, with an **Agroforestry Development Plan** for trees in hedges and fields. The NECP makes 32 mentions of agroforestry - many more than in any comparable national plan (EURAF [Research Report #139](#)).

10.2 Agroforestry in the EUDR Regulation.

Administration of the European Union Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) in France, has a "double-commande" structure, splitting responsibilities between two ministries: Ministry of Ecological Transition (MTE) - covering oversees environmental integrity, forest cover monitoring, and timber supply chain management, and the Ministry of Agriculture (MASA) - which covers compliance for agricultural commodities (cattle, soy, imported products). Enforcement is carried out through the *Douane* (Customs), which will act as the enforcement gatekeeper at the border, requiring a Due-Diligence Statement (DDS) reference number for all relevant customs declarations (EURAF [Research Report #65](#))

The regulation's cutoff date to establish the forest or non-forest status of all land parcels is December 31, 2020. Full due-diligence statements are required by December 30, 2025, for large and medium enterprises, and June 30, 2026, for small or micro enterprises. The ban on deforestation after the cutoff date applies to all operators.

The EUDR uses the FAO definition of forest¹⁷ (10% tree crown cover, 0.5ha block size and trees taller than 5 metres). The JRC Global Map of Forest in 2020 (Bourgoin et al. 2024) uses these thresholds and includes many areas of agroforestry, like orchards and silvopastoral systems, which are clearly agricultural systems rather than forestry. The EUDR allows operators to provide proof of agricultural use as an alternative to the JRC Global map, and in France, the best proof of this is inclusion within the *Registre Parcellaire Graphique* (RPG). This geospatial mapping system is administered by the French Ministry of Agriculture (MASA) through its Integrated Administration and Control System (TELEPAC)

¹⁷ Much better would have been to use the UNFCCC forest definition in the EUDR. This encompasses all national definitions globally, within a wider range of thresholds: "a minimum area of land of 0.05-1.0 hectares with tree crown cover (or equivalent stocking level) of more than 10-30 per cent with trees with the potential to reach a minimum height of 2-5 meters at maturity in situ".

A high-resolution [Masque Forêt](#) (v3) ([guide](#)) has been produced by the *Institut National de L'Information Graphique et Forestiere*.(IGN 2025)¹⁸, commissioned by the Ministry of Ecological Transition, which provides a high resolution vector map of forest parcels in France, excluding those with an agroforestry use registered in the RPG.

The “USAGE” field in RPG is for 2020 used to exclude the following “agroforestry” codes (marked in yellow in Figure 3):

- BOP (Bois pâturé) . *code retired in 2023*
- CEE (Chênaie entretenue par des porcins ou des petits ruminants) - *code retired in 2023*
- CAE (Châtaigneraie entretenue par des porcins ou des petits ruminants) - *code retired in 2023*
- PPH (Prairie permanente – herbe prédominante)
- SPL (Surface pastorale - ressources fourragères ligneuses prédominantes)
- SPH (Surface pastorale - herbe prédominante et ressources fourragères ligneuses présentes)

The map produced (Figure 3) is a **big step forward**, but there may still be a risk of inclusion of olive groves (OLIV), vineyards (VIN) fruit trees (VRG, VRC) nurseries (PEP), and no account has yet been made of the “Infrastructures Agro-Ecologiques” (IAE) layer - including the following codes, which are particularly important in northern France.

- HIE Haies (Hedges) Line Max width 20m. No gaps > 5m.
- ALI Alignement d'arbres (Tree Line) Line. Spacing < 5m between crowns.
- ISO Arbre isolé (Isolated Tree). Point. Canopy diameter > 4m.
- BOS Bosquets (Groves) Polygon Area between 10 ares and 50 ares
- MARE Mares (Ponds) Polygon Area < 0.5 ha. Natural banks (no concrete).
- FOS Fossés (Ditches) Line - Natural earth. Max width 6m.
- MURE Murets (Stone Walls) Line - Traditional stone walls.
- BOR Bordure de champ (Field Border) Polygon - Strip between crop and edge (buffer).
- BTA Bande Tampon (Buffer Strip). Polygon. Mandatory strip along watercourses (usually 5m+).

Figure 3 showing forest parcels (green) meeting the French definition (>0.5ha, 10% tree cover, trees > 5m when mature) and agroforestry parcels (yellow) which meet the same thresholds but are registered as agriculture in the French Land Parcel Information System (RPG). Red zones are urban forests. The date of collection of data depends on the Department and ranges from 2019-2022.

¹⁸ Machine translated to English here (to come)

10.3 Agroforestry in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework

The EU is developing a Carbon Removals Certification Framework, and a Carbon Farming Delegated Act for “agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils” ([link](#)); “afforestation” ([link](#)) and “peatland rewetting” ([EURAF Policy Briefing #20](#)). This will offer great opportunities for financial support to agroforestry beyond the 5-6 years when CAP incentives are available, but will also bring requirements for robust monitoring and creation of a management plan to guarantee biodiversity benefits and “no significant harm” to other environmental indicators

Ratification of Regulation (EU) 2024/3012, establishing the Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming, and carbon storage in products (CRCF), is a watershed moment for European climate policy. For France, a Member State with a mature, pre-existing domestic voluntary carbon market—the Label Bas-Carbone (LBC)—the implementation of the CRCF represents less of a genesis and more of a complex systemic metamorphosis.

The French Ministry of Ecological Transition (MTE), acting as the likely National Competent Authority, is currently orchestrating a strategic alignment of the LBC with the CRCF’s stringent “QU.A.L.I.T.Y” criteria (Quantification, Additionality, Long-term storage, Sustainability). This alignment is evidenced by the regulatory shifts observed in late 2025, specifically the decree modifying the LBC to transition from “emission reductions” to “carbon credits,” a semantic pivot necessary for European fungibility.

For the agroforestry sector, the transition implies a rigorous upgrading of Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) protocols. The draft EU methodologies for “Agriculture and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils” ([April 2025](#)) introduce Tier 3 modeling requirements and statistical sampling intensities that far exceed current domestic practices. Furthermore, the coexistence of the LBC with international standards such as Verra’s VCS (specifically the new VM0047 methodology for afforestation, reforestation, and revegetation - ARR) and Gold Standard creates a competitive, multi-layered landscape. A separate report has been produced which maps the administrative architecture, the technical gaps between French and EU standards, and the operational reality for farmers and project developers navigating this evolving ecosystem ([EURAF Research Report #35](#)).

10.4 Agroforestry in the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR)

All Member States are required to send a draft Nature Restoration Plan to Brussels by 1.9.2026. The most recent Habitats Directive reporting for France showed that 81% of habitats were in an unfavourable (poor or bad) condition, with more than 80% for all habitats in a “poor or bad” condition (EEA 2021). The Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) suggests biodiversity indicators for agricultural and forest diversity. One of the three agricultural biodiversity indicators is “area of high diversity landscape features”, and issues of how to define the meaning of “high diversity” Commission Notice [C/2025/980](#). The NRR is inadequate in many ways, including this definition: which excludes “productive trees” unless they form part of “sustainable agroforestry systems”, but it does leave the option for Member States to propose their own indicators. It is therefore suggested that France should define “high diversity landscape features” in a way that existing “éléments topographiques” in SIGPAC¹⁹ can be mapped and monitored.. Further information on the implementation of the NRR in France and its implications for agroforestry are given in [EURAF Research Report #67](#).

10.5 Agroforestry, Nature Credits and Water Resilience

Agroforestry systems offer a wide range of ecosystem services, include enhanced climate mitigation, climate adaptation, improved biodiversity by providing habitats for various species, including pollinators and natural pest controllers; protection of soil resources against erosion through the stabilizing effect of tree roots, and

¹⁹Also referred to as *Éléments favorables à la biodiversité ou Infrastructures agroécologiques* (IAE). They comprise *Les haies* (Hedges), *Les mares* (Ponds), *Les bosquets* (Small copses/wooded patches), *Les arbres isolés ou alignés* (Isolated or aligned trees), *Les fossés* (Ditches), *Les bandes tampons* (Buffer strips) along watercourses (also under BCAE 4)

improved water cycles and quality See “*Agricultural Trees for Resilient Landscapes: a Vision for European Agroforestry*” ([EURAF 2025](#)). These benefits could be costed and included in agri-environmental incentives through methodologies being developed in the Commission's “*Roadmap Towards Nature Credits*” (7.7.25 - [COM 2025-374](#)) and “*Water Resilience Strategy*” (4.6.25 - [COM 2025-280](#)).

In September 2025, the French Council of Economic Analysis published a report ([2025](#)) on the valuation of non-market services provided by forests. The document proposes a method for monetarily assessing carbon sequestration and other ecosystem services (e.g., recreational services), in order to integrate them into national accounting—currently limited to "market services" related to forestry activity—and into the heritage value of forests. According to these estimates, the added value of French forests would triple by including ecosystem services. Timber production would rank second, behind recreational services and ahead of carbon sequestration (see opposite). The heritage value of stored carbon would amount to €380 billion, compared to only €139 billion estimated according to current conventions. The authors suggest considering an expansion of the scope of national accounting to better inform climate, forestry, and environmental policy choices.

Beyond environmental advantages, agroforestry offers substantial socio-economic benefits: it allows the diversification of farm income through products like timber, fruits, nuts, and fodder, alongside traditional agricultural outputs. This diversification can enhance the economic resilience of farms, particularly in the face of climate change and market volatility. Agroforestry also supports rural development by creating employment opportunities and maintaining diverse rural landscapes). The estimated area of agroforestry in France has been estimated as 1.56 Mha (den Herder et al. 2017) or 5.73% of the UAA of 27.5 Mha. This is one of the largest areas of wood pasture habitat in Europe, and is a crucial example for other countries of this traditional, multifunctional agroforestry system.

To calculate the environmental impact of agricultural practices open and up-to-date access to parcel based agricultural information is needed. The French RPG system is one of the most modern, open and comprehensive datasets of land use information in the EU. However, it is only “largely compliant” with the with the EU High Value Datasets Regulation (2023) since a dedicated, well documented API for querying RPG data does not yet seem to be available ([EURAF Research Report #8](#)).

11. SWOT Analysis for agroforestry in France

11.1 Strengths

1. **Unrivaled Scientific Ecosystem and Long-Term R&D** . The cornerstone of French agroforestry is its scientific credibility, anchored by the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) and CIRAD. This research is supported by a series of programmes carried out by a large number of technical institutes and field organizations such as Agrooof, the AFAF or Réseau Haie France. Unlike many nations where agroforestry remains a niche interest of NGOs, in France, it is a subject of "hard" science. Researchers have maintained long-term experimental stations, such as the Restinclières estate in Hérault, for decades. These sites provide irrefutable longitudinal data on key metrics like the Land Equivalent Ratio (LER), demonstrating that mixed tree-crop systems can achieve higher total biomass productivity than monocultures (INRAE 2022a). Current research programs go far beyond basic yield measurements. They are investigating complex physiological interactions, such as root plasticity in response to competition, where trees in agroforestry systems are forced to root deeper, thereby accessing water reserves unavailable to crops and reducing drought stress. Furthermore, specific research into the "barrier effect" of hedges against pesticide drift and their role as reservoirs for auxiliary fauna (natural pest predators) provides the empirical basis for public subsidies. The research projects concerns all production sectors in agriculture. This scientific knowledge allows the Ministry of Agriculture to defend agroforestry support measures in Brussels against accusations of distorting competition, framing them instead as payments for scientifically proven ecosystem services.

2. The "Pacte en faveur de la haie": Institutionalizing the Target. The formal launch of the Pacte en faveur de la haie (Pact for the Hedge) in 2023 marked a watershed moment in French agricultural policy. By establishing a quantified national target—a net gain of 50,000 km of linear hedges by 2030—the state elevated the hedgerow from a landscape amenity to a strategic infrastructure of national interest (MASA 2023a). This target acts as a "north star" for policy coherence, theoretically aligning the actions of the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Ecology, and regional water agencies. The significance of the Pact lies in its recognition of the "net" gain principle, acknowledging that planting alone is insufficient if destruction continues. The initial budget allocation of €110 million for 2024 provided a substantial, albeit debated, injection of capital into the sector. This institutionalization forces decentralized state services (DDT, DRAAF) to integrate hedge monitoring into their core missions, rather than treating it as a peripheral environmental concern. It validates the work of historical actors and provides a statutory lever for civil society to hold the government accountable for its environmental performance (MASA 2023b). Unfortunately, the Pact for the Hedge was largely abandoned for political reasons in 2025.

3. A Structured and Professionalized Civil Society. France benefits from an exceptionally structured civil society network, led by the *Association Française d'Agroforesterie* (AFAF) and the *Réseau Haie France* federation, but also by Technical Institutes (federated inside ACTA) and the Chambers of Agriculture, in all the regions. These are not loose advocacy groups but technical institutes that bridge the gap between national policy and farm-level implementation. They have developed standardized technical reference guides (*référentiels*) for planting costs, management techniques, and carbon quantification, which are now used by public authorities to calculate subsidy rates.⁸ This "meso-level" infrastructure is critical for scaling. The network organizes the *Concours Général Agricole des Pratiques Agro-écologiques*, a prestigious competition that valorizes farmers' know-how, turning agroecology into a source of professional pride rather than just regulatory compliance. Furthermore, these organizations manage large-scale deployment programs like *Replant'Haie*, demonstrating an operational capacity to execute multi-million euro planting schemes that the state administration often lacks. Their presence ensures that policy design is grounded in the agronomic realities of diverse territories, from the hedgerows of Brittany to the silvopastoral systems of the Massif Central (Concours Générale Agricole 2020).

4. Strategic Integration into the CAP 2023-2027. The French National Strategic Plan (PSN) for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027 has successfully codified agroforestry support into the heart of the subsidy architecture. Unlike previous periods where trees could penalize farmers by reducing their eligible area, the current framework actively incentivizes their presence. The inclusion of the "*Bonus Haie*" within the Eco-schemes (*Ecorégimes*) offers a direct financial reward—up to €20 per hectare—for the maintenance of agro-ecological infrastructures (IAE) (AFAF 2025). Crucially, the maintenance of the eligibility density threshold (maximum 100 trees/hectare) ensures that agroforestry parcels remain eligible for Basic Income Support for Sustainability (BISS). This regulatory clarity removes the perverse incentive to clear trees to maximize subsidy receipts. Additionally, the conditionality rules under BC AE 8 (Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions) explicitly forbid the cutting of hedges and trees during the bird breeding season (March 16 to August 15) and mandate the preservation of landscape features. This creates a regulatory "floor" that protects existing stock while the eco-schemes provide the "ceiling" of incentives for new planting.

5. The Label Bas-Carbone: A Gold Standard for Finance. France has established itself as a pioneer in the voluntary carbon market through the state-backed Label Bas-Carbone (LBC). The specific methodologies approved for hedgerows (*Méthode Haies* and *Méthode Agroforesterie Intraparcellaire*) and orchards provide a rigorous, government-verified framework for quantifying and monetizing carbon sequestration. This is a significant strength compared to the unregulated "Wild West" of international voluntary carbon markets (MASA 2022). The LBC methodology is comprehensive, accounting for carbon stored in biomass and soil, as well as emissions avoided through reduced fertilizer use. It allows projects to generate premium carbon credits, which are currently trading at relatively high prices (averaging around €34/tonne, significantly higher than international commodity carbon). This high price point reflects the integrity of the verification process and the associated co-benefits (biodiversity, water quality), making these credits highly attractive to French corporations seeking to fulfill their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) commitments.

locally. The existence of this framework creates a potential revenue stream for farmers that is decoupled from public budgets (ReSoil 2025).

6. Robust Regional Dynamics and Decentralized Funding While national policy sets the framework, the engine of French agroforestry often resides in the regions. Regional Councils (Conseils Régionaux) manage the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (FEADER) pillar, allowing them to tailor investment aids to local priorities. Regions like Brittany, Occitanie, and Nouvelle-Aquitaine have developed aggressive agroforestry strategies that top up European funds with regional budgets. The Breizh Bocage program in Brittany is an exemplary case of territorial action, having facilitated the planting of thousands of kilometers of hedges to combat water pollution and erosion. Similarly, Occitanie leverages FEADER funds to support vitiforestry projects aimed at climate adaptation. These regional programs often offer more attractive intervention rates (up to 80% or even 100% for non-productive investments) and include bonuses for young farmers or organic conversion. This decentralization ensures that support mechanisms are adapted to local pedoclimatic conditions and agricultural models.²⁰ EURAF [Research Report #135](#) summarises the complex relationship between regional authorities, departments and groups of municipalities in relation to the inclusion of agroforestry in climate adaptation planning.

7. Diversity of Agronomic Models and Applications French agroforestry is characterized by its diversity, which enhances the sector's resilience. It encompasses a wide spectrum of practices: traditional prés-vergers (meadow orchards) in Normandy, modern alley-cropping in the cereal plains of the Paris Basin, silvopastoralism in the Alps, and vitiforestry in the south. This variety means that agroforestry is not a "one-size-fits-all" solution but a versatile toolkit adaptable to different production systems.¹⁰ In the viticulture sector, for instance, the integration of trees and cover crops is being rapidly adopted not just for carbon, but to manage vine vigor and microclimate—essential for maintaining wine acidity in a warming climate. In livestock farming, the focus is on animal welfare (shade and shelter), which correlates with productivity gains. The existence of these varied, economically viable models demonstrates to skeptics that agroforestry is operational across the entire agricultural spectrum, not limited to marginal lands or hobby farms.¹⁰

8. Educational Integration and Cultural Shift. A profound generational and cultural shift is underway, supported by the integration of agroecology into the agricultural education system. The *Enseignement Agricole* (agricultural high schools and technical institutes) has revised curricula to include systemic approaches to agronomy, where trees are viewed as functional inputs rather than obstacles. The "Osé" platform (*Osez l'Agroécologie created by Solagro Association*) and "Arborécole" platform (created by Agrooft in collaboration with the Bergerie National which leads the knowledge transfer for all the public institutes) facilitates knowledge transfer and peer-to-peer learning (Concours Générale Agricole 2020). This educational foundation is crucial because it addresses the root cause of resistance: the post-war cultural programming that equated "clean" farming with treeless fields. Younger farmers, often referred to as Non-Issus du Milieu Agricole (NIMA - not from agricultural backgrounds), are entering the profession with a strong ecological motivation and without the historical prejudices against trees. This demographic renewal provides a fertile ground for policy uptake, as the demand for agroforestry support is increasingly driven from the bottom up by new entrants (Chesnaï-Girard 2025).

9. Emerging Bioeconomy Supply Chains. The economic case for agroforestry is being strengthened by the development of local bioeconomy supply chains, particularly for wood energy. The maintenance of hedges generates significant biomass (wood chips or plaquettes), which can be valorized in local heating networks (*chaufferies bois*) for municipalities, schools, or swimming pools. Sustainable Hedge Management Plans (*Plans de Gestion Durable des Haies launched by Réseau Haie France*) are increasingly linked to these local markets, turning hedge maintenance from a pure cost center into a revenue-generating activity. With rising fossil fuel prices, the value of local woody biomass has increased, providing a floor price for agroforestry by-products. This circular economy model reinforces the social license to operate, as farmers are seen as contributors to local energy sovereignty (AFAF 2023).

10. Corporate Engagement and "In-Setting" Major agri-food conglomerates with deep footprints in France—notably Nestlé, Danone, Yves Rocher Foundations and LVMH—have moved beyond superficial philanthropy to integrate regenerative agriculture into their core supply chains. This practice, known as "in-setting," involves investing directly in the farms that supply their raw materials.²⁵ Nestlé's "Sols Vivants" program and Danone's regenerative dairy initiatives provide technical assistance and financial incentives for farmers to plant trees and cover crops. LVMH has partnered with UNESCO in the "*Pour la beauté du vivant*" program to enhance biodiversity in its sourcing regions. The federation "*Fond pour l'Arbre*" is also important. These corporate initiatives have the advantage of offering long-term contracts and price premiums that public policy cannot always guarantee. They align market forces with policy goals, creating a multiplier effect that accelerates adoption among farmers who might be wary of purely state-led schemes (Groupe L'Occitane 2025).

11.2 Weaknesses - the friction of Implementation

1. The "Statut du Fermage" (Tenant Farming Statute). The single most formidable structural barrier to agroforestry in France is the statut du fermage. Enacted in 1946 to protect tenant farmers from arbitrary eviction, this legal framework governs the relationship between landowners (bailleurs) and tenant farmers (preneurs) for the 60%+ of French agricultural land that is rented. Under Articles L.411 et seq. of the Rural Code, a tenant strictly requires the written permission of the landowner to make permanent improvements, including planting trees. This requirement creates a massive bottleneck. Landowners are often reluctant to grant permission due to fears that trees will complicate future land sales, devalue the property for conventional farming, or grant the tenant entrenched rights that make lease termination difficult. Furthermore, the compensation mechanisms for the tenant at the end of the lease (indemnification for the value of the trees) are complex and often litigious. This legal rigidity effectively locks out the majority of French farmland from agile agroforestry adoption, as tenants are unwilling to invest in assets they do not own on land they might lose (RRAF 2018).

2. Administrative Dysfunctions and "Telepac" Anxiety. The digitization of the CAP declaration process via the "Telepac" platform has become a source of significant administrative distress. In the 2023 and 2024 campaigns, serious dysfunctions were reported, including the inability to correctly declare "structural modifications" to farms or update hedge features on digital maps. These technical failures led to delayed payments, forcing the administration to extend deadlines and creating cash-flow crises for farmers.³³ Beyond glitches, the system fosters a culture of anxiety regarding the "Right to Error" (*Droit à l'erreur*). Farmers fear that if the canopy of their trees grows too wide, satellite monitoring (Surface Monitoring System in Real Time) will flag the area as "non-eligible" for basic income support, triggering automated penalties. This leads to "preventative clearing" or over-pruning, where farmers aggressively cut back hedges to ensure they align perfectly with the digital layers of Telepac, undermining the ecological value the policy intends to support (Sanson 2023).

3. Budgetary Volatility and "Stop-and-Go" Financing. Trust is the currency of long-term investment, and recent budgetary oscillations have devalued it. The political saga surrounding the 2025 Finance Bill (PLF 2025) exposed the fragility of state commitments. The government's initial proposal to slash the Pacte en faveur de la haie budget by 72%—from €110 million to €30 million—sent a shockwave through the sector. Although parliamentary amendments (notably in the Senate) sought to restore funding to €80 million or more, the damage to confidence was done. Agroforestry nurseries, which need to plan stock years in advance, cannot operate in a "stop-and-go" funding environment. If subsidy windows open and close unpredictably based on annual fiscal arbitration, farmers will disengage. The administrative cost of preparing complex grant applications is too high to risk rejection due to sudden budget cuts (Anon 2025).

4. Critical Shortage of Technical Advisors. While the quality of French expertise is world-class, the quantity is insufficient to meet national targets. There is a severe bottleneck in "human infrastructure." The number of specialized agroforestry technicians capable of designing systems, drafting management plans, and navigating the specificities of local hydrology and biodiversity is far below what is needed to plant 50,000 km of hedges. Many Chambers of Agriculture are still transitioning from conventional production-oriented

advice to systemic agro-ecological support. The specialized networks (Réseau Haie France, AFAF) are saturated. This means that willing farmers often face long wait times for feasibility studies. Agroforestry cannot be automated; it requires bespoke design (species selection, orientation, pruning regime) adapted to each plot. The lack of boots on the ground is a primary constraint on scaling up (AFAF 2023). The Pacte pour la Haie allowed to increase the number of advisors from 2023 to 2024, but the sudden abandonment of this programme caused a halt to the hiring of new advisors in 2025.

5. The Economic "Valley of Death". Agroforestry projects suffer from a mismatch between cash outflows and inflows. The initial establishment costs—seedlings, protection tubes, mulch, and labor—are high. While subsidies may cover a percentage of these costs, they rarely cover 100%, and they are often paid as reimbursements long after the expense is incurred. More critically, there is a "Valley of Death" in the first 5-10 years where the trees are not yet productive (no fruit or wood revenue) but compete with the crops for light and water, potentially reducing short-term yields. Maintenance costs (pruning, weeding) are incurred annually without immediate return. The banking sector lacks specific financial products (grace periods, specialized loans) to bridge this gap, forcing farmers to self-finance the transition and limiting adoption to the most capitalized enterprises (Dossa et al. 2025). Climate hazards reinforce this economic weight when they cause an increase in the mortality rate of young trees planted.

6. Regulatory Ambiguity: Forest vs. Agriculture A persistent grey area exists between "agricultural land with trees" and "forest." This definitional ambiguity creates significant legal risk for farmers. If an agroforestry plot becomes too dense (canopy cover exceeds a certain percentage), it risks being reclassified as "forest" by the administration. Once classified as forest, the land falls under the strict regime of the Code Forestier, which makes clearing trees (deforestation) illegal and changes inheritance and tax rules. This fear of "irreversibility" acts as a powerful deterrent. Farmers may limit tree density or avoid planting altogether to ensure they retain full agricultural control over their land in the future (MAAF 2023).

7. Mechanization Constraints and Physical Lock-in. French agriculture is highly capitalized and mechanized, particularly in the large cereal plains (*Grandes Cultures*). The machinery—combine harvesters, sprayers with 40m booms—is designed for large, open, rectangular fields. The reintroduction of trees acts as a physical constraint that reduces operational efficiency. Navigating around tree rows reduces the work rate (hectares per hour), complicates turns, and requires precision driving (though GPS helps). In a sector where labour is scarce and margins are thin, the "convenience penalty" of working around trees is a significant barrier. Farmers often cite the loss of efficiency and the complexity of managing field borders as primary reasons for rejecting agroforestry, despite acknowledging the theoretical benefits (Dossa et al. 2025).

8. Bureaucratic Silos and Contradictory Injunctions. The administration of the rural environment is fragmented across multiple agencies with conflicting mandates. The Ministry of Agriculture promotes production; the Ministry of Ecology (and its diverse agencies like the OFB - French Biodiversity Office) enforces protection; Water Agencies fund water quality initiatives. A farmer might receive a subsidy from a Water Agency to plant a hedge but face a fine from the OFB for maintaining it in a way that disturbs a protected species. The lack of a unified "**Guichet Unique**" (One-Stop Shop) increases the transaction costs for farmers, who must navigate different reporting requirements, deadlines, and definitions of what constitutes a compliant hedge (Envergo 2024).

9. Data Gaps and Inventory Deficiencies. Despite the advanced state of French administration, there is a surprising lack of high-frequency, granular data on agroforestry assets. The IGN (National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information) tracks forests meticulously, but "trees outside forests" (TOF) are harder to monitor. Estimates of hedge length are often based on periodic extrapolations rather than real-time inventory. This data gap makes it difficult to accurately evaluate the net impact of policies like the Pacte Haie. Is the country actually gaining net kilometers, or is new planting being silently outpaced by destruction in zones not subject to strict monitoring? This lack of visibility hampers evidence-based policy adjustments (Balny et al. 2015).

10. Sociological Inertia and Peer Pressure. Finally, a deep-seated sociological weakness persists: the cultural aesthetic of the "good farmer." For generations, agricultural modernization (*modernisme*) was associated with the removal of obstacles, the straightening of streams, and the creation of clean, geometric fields. In many rural communities, a field with trees is culturally coded as "messy," "backward," or "poorly maintained." Peer pressure is a potent force; a farmer planting trees in a region dominated by open plains may face ridicule or skepticism from neighbors and cooperatives. Overcoming this identity-based resistance is often harder than overcoming economic barriers, as it challenges the professional self-image of the conventional farmer (Montero-de-Oliveira et al. 2025).

11.3 Opportunities - aligning markets and climate reality

The external environment offers a unique window of opportunity. The convergence of climate urgency, market demand for sustainability, and European regulatory pressure is creating a pull factor that could override the domestic structural weaknesses

1. Scaling the Voluntary Carbon Market. The demand for high-quality carbon credits is exploding as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) forces companies to account for their emissions. French agroforestry credits, backed by the Label Bas-Carbone, are positioned as a premium product. Trading at an average of €34.5/tonne, they command a price far higher than international offsets.¹⁷ There is an opportunity to scale this market significantly. If the price of carbon continues to rise, the revenue from credits could eventually rival CAP subsidies, providing a completely private financing mechanism for planting. The "charismatic" nature of these credits—which offer visible biodiversity and local social benefits—makes them ideal for French companies looking to invest in their own territory ("contribution" rather than just "compensation") (Martel et al. 2025).

2. Payments for Ecosystem Services (PSE) beyond Carbon. Water Agencies (Agences de l'Eau) are increasingly experimenting with Payments for Ecosystem Services (PSE) schemes that pay farmers for the performance of environmental services, particularly water purification and flood mitigation. Unlike traditional subsidies that pay for the act of planting (an asset), PSE schemes pay for the service provided (a flow). There is an immense opportunity to generalize this model. If local municipalities and water syndicates pay farmers an annual fee for the hydraulic buffering capacity of their hedges, the hedge becomes a productive asset. This creates a recurrent income stream that solves the maintenance cost issue and aligns the farmer's economic interest with the public good (Bailly et al. 2022; Marei Viti et al. 2024).

3. European Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy 2030. The European Union acts as a powerful external driver. The EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 sets ambitious targets, including planting 3 billion trees and restoring 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers. This supranational pressure forces France to maintain its commitments regardless of domestic political shifts. This context opens up access to direct EU funding streams (LIFE projects, Horizon Europe) that can bypass national budget constraints. It also creates a competitive dynamic where France has the opportunity to position itself as the "best in class" implementer, potentially attracting more EU investment into its rural territories. The upcoming Nature Restoration Law will further legally oblige member states to restore ecosystems, cementing the role of agroforestry in national law EURAF [Policy Briefing 18](#).

4. Import Substitution and Food Sovereignty (Nuts & Fruits). France currently imports a significant portion of its nuts (walnuts, hazelnuts, almonds) and certain fruits. There is a strategic opportunity to relocate this production through agroforestry systems. The "*Plan Protéines*" and various food sovereignty initiatives support this shift (France Stratégie 2024)). Developing structured supply chains for agroforestry products—such as "*Agroforestry Walnuts*" or "*Bocage Cider*"—can tap into the consumer demand for local, traceable food. ADEME-funded projects are currently mapping production basins to identify the best zones for these crops.²⁰ Diversifying farm income with high-value tree crops provides a hedge against yield

²⁰ <https://www.instaofr.com/appel-offre/production-agroforestiere-fruits-coque-09-25-france-hexagonale-L4>

volatility observed in monocropping systems. But the main goal could be the answer offered by agroforestry diversity to allow biocontrol systems.

5. Adaptation as the Primary Driver (The "Shade" Economy). As climate change accelerates, the motivation for agroforestry is shifting from "mitigation" (carbon) to "adaptation" (survival). In the summer of 2022 and 2023, the shading effect of trees was visibly correlated with the survival of crops and the welfare of livestock during extreme heatwaves. There is an opportunity to reframe the narrative: trees are the farmer's insurance policy. In viticulture, shade is becoming the only viable tool to prevent alcohol levels from spiking due to heat stress. Insurance companies and banks may soon begin to view agroforestry farms as lower-risk assets, potentially offering better rates. This "adaptation imperative" may drive adoption.

6. Digital Innovation and Precision Agroforestry. Technological advancements offer the chance to resolve the "mechanization vs. trees" conflict. Precision agriculture tools, including RTK-GPS guidance and autonomous robots, can navigate complex environments much better than human-driven tractors. Startups are developing digital tools to automate the design of agroforestry parcels, ensuring optimal spacing for machinery. Furthermore, improvements in satellite monitoring (Sentinel data) and AI analysis can streamline the inventory process, allowing the administration to monitor hedges without physical inspections. This could drastically reduce the administrative burden and the fear of "Telepac anomalies"

7. Blended Finance Vehicles. The rise of corporate interest allows for the creation of "blended finance" vehicles where public money de-risks projects and private money scales them. Funds like the *Fonds pour l'Arbre* allow diverse donors to pool resources. This model allows for projects that are more ambitious than what public aid alone could support. It can bridge the "Valley of Death" by offering upfront cash payments rather than reimbursements. The opportunity lies in structuring these funds to be accessible to all farmers, not just those in the supply chains of major multinationals

8. Legislative Simplification (Loi d'Orientation Agricole). The current political moment, characterized by farmer protests and the government's response via the *Loi d'Orientation Agricole* (Agricultural Orientation Law), offers a window for regulatory overhaul. The government has explicitly committed to "simplifying" the norms surrounding hedges. There is a tangible opportunity to push for a "Single Declaration" system that harmonizes the definition of hedges across the Environmental and Rural codes. If successful, this would unclog the system, releasing a backlog of projects that are currently stalled by red tape. The simplification of Article 14 regarding hedge management is a key legislative battleground that could yield positive results

9. Energy Sovereignty and Biomass. The geopolitical shock of the Ukraine war and the subsequent energy crisis has renewed interest in local energy sovereignty. Hedges represent a strategic reserve of distributed renewable energy. Structuring the "hedge-to-boiler" supply chain offers rural territories a way to insulate themselves from global gas price spikes. This provides a compelling "sovereignty" argument for agroforestry that appeals to political conservatives and progressives alike, potentially securing cross-party support for

10. Demographic Renewal and "NIMA". Half of French farmers will retire in the coming decade. The new entrants replacing them are statistically more likely to be interested in agroecology. These *Nouveaux Installés* often prioritize environmental health and direct marketing over industrial volume.²⁰ This demographic turnover is the ultimate opportunity. By targeting installation aids (*Dotation Jeune Agriculteur* - DJA) specifically toward agroforestry projects, the state can reshape the landscape for the next 30 years. These new farmers act as living laboratories; their success will prove the concept to the skepticism of the older generation (Concours Générale Agricole 2020).

11.4 Threats: External Shocks and Implementation Risks

The path to 50,000 km of hedges is not guaranteed. Significant threats—biological, economic, and political—loom over the sector.

1. Biological Vulnerability: Pathogens and Pests. The most acute physical threat is biological. French tree stocks are currently under assault from emerging pathogens. *Chalara fraxinea* (Ash Dieback) has devastated

ash populations, a traditional hedgerow species. *Scolytes* (Bark Beetles) are ravaging spruce and pine in the East. Planting massive monocultures of hedges (e.g., only oak or hazel) invites disaster. The narrowing of genetic diversity in nursery stock, due to the sudden spike in demand from the Pacte Haie, exacerbates this risk. A failure in biosecurity or genetic diversity could result in mass die-offs in 10-15 years, discrediting the policy and wasting millions in public funds.²¹

2. Climate Velocity vs. Tree Adaptation. Climate change is accelerating faster than trees can adapt. The "climate velocity" (the speed at which suitable climate zones move north) outpaces the natural migration of forests. Recent planting campaigns have already seen mortality rates of 30-50% in young seedlings due to spring droughts and heatwaves.⁵⁶ There is a profound risk that the species being planted today—based on historical climate data—will be physiologically unsuited to the climate of 2050. If these investments fail due to heat stress, the "adaptation" strategy collapses. The "adaptation lag" is a fundamental threat to the biological viability of the Pacte Haie (INRAE 2022b).

3. Land Competition: The Agrivoltaics Boom. A potent economic threat comes from the renewable energy sector. Agrivoltaics (solar panels on farmland) offer rental rates that dwarf agricultural returns. Developers in regions like Aveyron offer rents of up to €3,000/ha/year, compared to €150-200/ha for standard farming leases.⁶³ There is a real risk that "trees" are replaced by "panels" as the preferred provider of shade. While some agrivoltaic systems are virtuous, many are industrial energy plants with token agriculture. The financial dominance of the energy sector could displace agroforestry, consuming the land and political bandwidth available for multi-use systems. The Chambers of Agriculture are wary of this "cannibalization" of productive land (Hrabanski et al. 2024).

4. Political Austerity and Budget Cuts. The near-death experience of the Pacte Haie budget in the PLF 2025 illustrates the threat of austerity. In a context of national debt reduction, environmental programs are often seen as "nice to have" rather than essential. The threat is that agroforestry becomes an adjustment variable. If the budget is cut or delayed, the momentum built since 2023 will dissipate. The "stop-and-go" funding cycle destroys the private sector ecosystem (nurseries, technicians) that relies on steady public demand. Without a multi-year programming law, the sector is always one budget cycle away from paralysis.

5. "Simplification" turning into Deregulation. The political response to farmer anger involves "simplification." While reducing bureaucracy is necessary, there is a threat that this creates a loophole for destruction. If the protections of BCAE 8 or Article 14 are watered down to appease protests, it could unleash a wave of hedge removal (OKLIMA 2025). Farmers, fearing future constraints, might preemptively clear features before new rules come into effect. A "simplification" that removes the requirement to declare hedge removal would make monitoring impossible and negate the net gain targets.²²

6. Greenwashing and "Green Deserts". As corporate money floods the sector, the risk of greenwashing increases. Projects designed solely to maximize carbon credits often favour fast-growing species (poplar, eucalyptus) over complex, biodiverse native hedges. If the agroforestry boom results in "green deserts"—rows of timber trees with no biodiversity value—the environmental credibility of the sector will be destroyed. A scandal involving "fake" agroforestry credits could toxify the Label Bas-Carbone brand and drive away investors (Martel et al. 2025).

7. Land Fragmentation (Indivision). Land ownership in France is heavily fragmented due to inheritance laws. Many parcels are held in indivision (joint ownership) by multiple heirs who may not agree on management. Getting the signature of a dozen distant cousins to authorize a long-term tree planting project is often impossible. This legal paralysis threatens to block projects on a significant portion of the territory, particularly in regions with a history of smallholdings. As the population ages, this fragmentation worsens, leaving land in a state of decision-making limbo (Léger-Bosch et al. 2020).

²¹ <https://www.cnpf.fr/nos-actions-nos-outils/focus-sur-quelques-projets/le-frene-face-la-chalarose>

²² <https://www.senat.fr/rap/a24-187/a24-1876.html>

8. Labour Shortages in Rural Zones. Maintaining hedges is labor-intensive. It requires pruning, coppicing, and shredding. However, rural France is suffering from a severe labor shortage. The "artisanal" nature of hedge management clashes with the industrial efficiency of modern farming. If the labor force to manage the trees does not exist, farmers will view the trees as a burden. Overgrown, unmanaged hedges encroach on fields and eventually interfere with machinery, leading to their removal. The lack of a structured "hedge maintenance service sector" is a critical threat to the longevity of the planted systems (de Menthiere et al. 2023)

9. High Commodity Prices Incentivizing Monoculture. Agroforestry adoption is counter-cyclical. When wheat or corn prices are high (as seen in 2022), every square meter of arable land is precious. The opportunity cost of planting a tree row—which takes land out of production—rises. A sustained period of high global commodity prices could stall the transition. Farmers will prioritize maximizing short-term harvest volume over long-term resilience. The economic signal from the Chicago Board of Trade often speaks louder than the signal from the Ministry of Ecology (MAAF 2025).

10. Uneven Implementation Across EU Borders. While the CAP is European, its implementation is national. If France implements strict "gold-plated" environmental rules (surtransposition) while neighbors like Spain or Poland adopt more flexible approaches, French farmers will feel competitively disadvantaged. This perception of unfairness creates political backlash. If French farmers feel they are being "punished" with trees while their competitors are not, the legitimacy of the policy erodes, leading to non-compliance and protests (Dubois 2016).⁴⁵

12. Recommendations for Action

1. **Re-establish and secure multi-year funding for the Pacte en faveur de la haie to stabilize the agroforestry sector**
2. **Convene a national, multi-stakeholder task force (including APCA, FNSEA, CR, CF etc) to modernize the Statut du Fermage for agroecological transitions.**
3. **Simplify the procedures used to reduce area payments in parcels with scattered tree cover.** While the ability to flag tree lines as landscape features is welcome the rules identifying scattered trees and shrubs are still too rigid, particularly when these are edible by stock, and where grazing is vital as a fire-control measure.
4. **Establish a departmental Guichet Unique (One-Stop Shop) powered by AI and GIS to streamline agroforestry deployment.** This could help farmers negotiate the complex landscape of multiple funders and regulations with planting options given which are specific to their pedoclimatic conditions.
5. **Expand the Guichet Unique infrastructure into an environmental modelling tool to lay the groundwork for future "nature credits.** This could : a) to identify parcels of high environmental value and b) add model-based predictions of environmental stress such as nutrient load, hydrology, biodiversity impact and erosion risk.
6. **Finalize a comprehensive national agroforestry GIS system to accurately distinguish agricultural tree cover from forest parcels.** The excellent MET-IGN "Masque Forêt (v3)" helps separate agroforestry parcels for EUDR reporting, but it Infrastructures Agro Écologiques (IAE) and Surfaces Pastorales Herbacées (SPH) parcels with high tree cover remain to be included. This integrated agroforestry map was planned in Axis 1 of the "Plan de développement de l'agroforesterie" (2025-2020), and has not yet been achieved.
7. **Designate the Registre Parcellaire Graphique (RPG) as the single source of truth for EU Nature Restoration reporting on agricultural land to prevent data duplication.** Some indicators in the NRR, such as "High Diversity Landscape Features", change the rules for data collection - to avoid confusion the RPG should be the single source of data for reporting.
8. **Develop a collaborative, public GIS mapping system to consolidate France's agroforestry network.** RPG data in CAP agroforestry interventions should be combined with databases on agroforestry farmers collated nationally by APCA, AFAP and Réseau Haies and, if agreed by farmers, made available in a public GIS system.

9. **Highlight the departments which have higher proportions of “tree deserts” on agricultural land.** MASA should publish lists of departments with greatest need for agricultural tree planting and most scope for regional supplements to existing incentives.
10. **Climate Adaptation Strategies should stress agroforestry options.** The current approach in France is inconsistent. The *Stratégie Française Énergie-Climat* (SFEC - July 2024) mentioned agroforestry 28 times in 305 pages but the *Plan National d'Adaptation au Changement Climatique* (PNACC3 - March 2025) gives a single mention in 388 pages.
11. **Support for new farmers (NIMAs) is needed to access agricultural land and agroforestry support.** Existing initiatives like Terre de liens and SAFERS. Options include "Portage de Foncier" (Land Carrying) with "Land Observatories" which allow private investors to buy land and lease it to NIMAs with a "right to buy" option 10–15 years later. This gives the farmer time to establish tree crops (fruit, timber, or nuts) before taking on the debt of land ownership.
12. **An action plan for evolutionary resilience is needed for damaging tree diseases.** Including continuing sanitary felling, vector control and pheromone trapping but extending to greater intraspecific diversity. Greater use of resilient planes and chestnut trees is needed. The 10-20-30 rule²³ has been suggested for planting trees outside the forest. The concept of “localness” for tree planting stock has to be rethought and databases provided of which species and provenances will respond to future climates
13. **Establish a comprehensive statistical framework for trees planted outside forests to resolve current EU reporting deficits.** France provides no information to the EU on forestry or agroforestry tree planting (Result Indicator 17) since planting is now met entirely from “national resources”. This even applies to the planting of woody landscape features - where statistics are unavailable.
14. **The Registre Parcellaire Graphique (RPG) should increasingly be linked to the Rural Cadastre.** This will allow for coordination of a forest versus agriculture parcel map and to map areas of agriculture which are too small to be part of the CAP Agricultural system, but are nevertheless important for mapping of land use, and the identification of owners in the case of fire-control measures.
15. **Fund targeted R&D into the mechanization of lower-branch pruning (élagage) and branch harvesting** to eliminate the primary labour bottleneck in high-stem agroforestry
16. **Improve farmer access to high-value timber market data to incentivize formative pruning.**
17. **Include CAP intervention codes in the TELEPAC system,** allowing the subsidies to be related to measurements of environmental impact, for the time.
18. **Establish a Public-Private Purchasing Consortium dedicated to agroforestry carbon credits ("Buyers Club)** Carbon markets are currently depressed with few buyers for Label Bas Carbon. By pooling public capital and private CSR (*Responsabilité Sociétale des Entreprises*) investments, this consortium would guarantee the ex-ante (upfront) pre-purchase of carbon removals.
19. **Design an “Agroforestry Carbon Farming Starter Pack” to integrate with later carbon removal certification.** Where ecoschemes can be used to plan agroforestry and take baseline measurements in year 0, investment measures can finance tree-planting in year 1 and CAP agri-environment measures can annual maintenance support for years 1-5, followed by eventual adoption into a carbon farming scheme like LBC, without concern over “double funding” or “financial additionality”.
20. **Incentivize the deployment of portable biochar kilns** for wood prunings and thinnings through cooperative sharing models (CUMAs) and integrate on-farm biochar production into the Label Bas-Carbone

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²³ no more than 10% of any single species, no more than 20% of any single Genus, no more than 30% of any single family.

14. References

- AFAF, 2022. Agroforesterie définition - Association Française d'agroforesterie. *Agroforesterie Association Française*. Available at: <https://www.agroforesterie.fr/agroforesterie-definition/> [Accessed November 22, 2025].
- AFAF, 2025. Les Ligneux Agricoles et la PAC 2023-27. Available at: <https://www.agroforesterie.fr/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/les-ligneux-agricoles-et-la-pac-2023-2027-.pdf>.
- AFAF, 2023. *Rapport d'Activité*, Association Française d'Agroforesterie. Available at: <https://www.agroforesterie.fr/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/rapport-dactivite-association-francaise-dagroforesterie-2023.pdf>.
- Anon, 2025. Aperçu de l'amendement. *senat.fr*. Available at: https://www.senat.fr/amendements/2024-2025/143/Amdt_II-243.html [Accessed November 30, 2025].
- Bailly, M.-L. et al., 2022. Se lancer dans une démarche de OSE avec des cikkectufs d'agriculteurs: enseignements Méthodologiques de Project LABPSE. Available at: <https://trame.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/GUIDE-METHODO.pdf>.
- Balny, P., Domallain, D. & Galbert, M., 2015. *Promotion des systèmes agroforestiers*,
- Bourgoin, C. et al., 2024. *Mapping global forest cover of the year 2020 to support the EU regulation on deforestation-free supply chains*, Joint Research Centre. Available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC136960> [Accessed November 23, 2025].
- Burgess, P. et al., 2018. AGFORWARD project final report. Available at: <https://dspace.lib.cranfield.ac.uk/handle/1826/13475> [Accessed December 6, 2021].
- Chesnais-Girard, L., 2025. *Priorité à l'installation et à la souveraineté alimentaire 2025*, Dossier de presse. Available at: <https://www.intercommunalites.fr/app/uploads/2025/02/RGIONB1.pdf>.
- Concours Générale Agricole, 2020. Dossier de Presse Février 2020 - Concours des Pratiques Agro-écologiques - Agroforesterie Prairies & Parcours. Available at: https://reseauhaies.fr/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/CPAE_DP_260220_light.pdf.
- Dossa, K.F., Bissonnette, J.-F. & Soudet, T., 2025. Comparison of Governance Policies for Agroforestry Initiatives: Lessons Learned from France and Quebec. *Sustainability*, 17(13), p.6114. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su17136114> [Accessed November 30, 2025].
- Dubois, J.-J., 2016. L'évolution des systèmes agroforestiers en France - leur rôle en Agroécologie. *Pollution Atmosphérique*. Available at: https://www.appa.asso.fr/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Dubois_2016.pdf.
- Dupraz, C. et al., 2018. Temperate agroforestry: the European way. In A. Gordon, S. M. Newman, & B. Coleman, eds. *Temperate Agroforestry Systems*. CABI: Wallingford, pp. 98–152. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1079/9781780644851.0098>.
- EEA, 2021. Conservation status of habitats under the EU Habitats Directive. *EEA Indicators*. Available at: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/conservation-status-of-habitats-under> [Accessed November 23, 2025].
- Envergo, 2024. Guichet unique de la haie (Envergo agricole). *beta.gouv.fr*. Available at: <https://beta.gouv.fr/startups/guichet-unique-de-la-haie-envergo-agricole.html> [Accessed November 30, 2025].
- FAO, 2025. Serbia launches FOREST Invest project to boost energy security and climate resilience. *FAO in the Republic of Serbia*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/serbia/news/detail/officially-starts-the-forest-invest-project/en> [Accessed November 3, 2025].
- Feranec, J. et al., 2016. *European Landscape Dynamics: CORINE Land Cover Data*, CRC Press. Available at: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-EsHBDAAAQBAJ>.
- France Stratégie, 2024. *Le Développement des protéines végétales*, Comité d'évaluation du plan France Relance - Rapport final. Available at: https://www.strategie-plan.gouv.fr/files/files/Publications/Rapport/fs-2024-rapport-france_relance_vol_ii_10_proteines_vegetales_0.pdf.
- García de Jalón, S. et al., 2018. How is agroforestry perceived in Europe? An assessment of positive and negative aspects by stakeholders. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(4), pp.829–848. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0116-3>.
- Groupe L'Occitane, 2025. Environmental, Social and Governance FY2025 Report. Available at: https://group.loccitane.com/sites/default/files/2025-08/L%E2%80%99OCCITANE%20Group%20ESG%20Report%20FY2025_0.pdf.
- den Herder, M. et al., 2017. Current extent and stratification of agroforestry in the European Union. *Agriculture, ecosystems & environment*, 241, pp.121–132. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0167880917301159>.
- den Herder, M. et al., 2025. Methods to record agroforestry areas and greenhouse gas emissions in the EU (DigitAF Deliverable 1.3). Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15776640> [Accessed July 24, 2025].
- Hrabanski, M., Verdeil, S. & Ducastel, A., 2024. Agrivoltaics in France: the multi-level and uncertain regulation of an energy decarbonisation policy. *Review of Agricultural Food and Environmental Studies*, 105(1), pp.45–71. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s41130-024-00204-1>.

- IGN, 2025. *Masque Foret v1 - Descriptif de contenu et de livraison*, Institut National de Information Géographique et Forestiers. Available at: https://geoservices.ign.fr/sites/default/files/2025-10/DC_DL_Masque_Foret_v1.pdf.
- INRAE, 2022a. Agroforesterie : des arbres pour une agriculture durable. *INRAE Institutionnel*. Available at: <https://www.inrae.fr/actualites/agroforesterie-arbres-agriculture-durable> [Accessed November 24, 2025].
- INRAE, 2022b. Agroforestry: trees provide a way forward for sustainable farming. *INRAE Institutionnel*. Available at: <https://www.inrae.fr/en/news/agroforestry-trees-provide-way-forward-sustainable-farming> [Accessed October 10, 2023].
- Klorane Botanical Foundation, 2019. Qu'est-ce que l'agroforesterie ? *Klorane Botanical Foundation - 15 rue Théron Périé81106 Castres Cedex - France*. Available at: <https://www.kloranebotanical.foundation/comprendre-et-preserver-la-biodiversite/agriculture-et-biodiversite/quest-ce-que-lagroforesterie> [Accessed November 22, 2025].
- Léger-Bosch, C. et al., 2020. Changes in property-use relationships on French farmland: A social innovation perspective. *Land use policy*, 94(104545), p.104545. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104545> [Accessed November 30, 2025].
- MAAF, 2025. *Building with Wood: Environmental and Economic Potential*, Service de la Statistique et de la Prospective. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/telecharger/148876>.
- MAAF, 2023. Régime exempté de notification SA.107473 relatif aux aides dans le secteur forestier en lien avec le plan stratégique national de la PAC pour la période 2023-2027. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/telecharger/137706>.
- Marei Viti, M. et al., 2024. Introducing the progress monitoring tools of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. *Ecological indicators*, 164(112147), p.112147. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1470160X24006046>.
- Martel, S. et al., 2025. *Le Label Bas-Carbone: quel bilan après 6 ans d'existence ?*, Institute for Climate Economics. Available at: https://www.i4ce.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Le-Label-bas-carbone-quel-bilan-apres-6-ans-dexistence_V1.pdf.
- MASA, 2022. Les méthodes agricoles du label bas-carbone. *Ministère de l'Agriculture et de la Souveraineté alimentaire*. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/les-methodes-agricoles-du-label-bas-carbone> [Accessed September 22, 2025].
- MASA, 2023a. Pacte en faveur de la haie.
- MASA, 2023b. Présentation du « Pacte en faveur de la haie » doté d'un budget de 110 M€ dès 2024. *Ministère de l'Agriculture, de l'Agro-alimentaire et de la Souveraineté alimentaire*. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/presentation-du-pacte-en-faveur-de-la-haie-dote-dun-budget-de-110-meu-des-2024> [Accessed November 24, 2025].
- de Menthière, C. et al., 2023. *La haie, levier de la planification écologique*, Available at: <https://www.vie-publique.fr/files/rapport/pdf/289211.pdf>.
- MinAg, 2025. L'agroforesterie en France. *Ministère de l'Agriculture, de l'Agro-alimentaire et de la Souveraineté alimentaire*. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/lagroforesterie-en-france> [Accessed November 22, 2025].
- Montero-de-Oliveira, F.-E. et al., 2025. Agroforestry as land-based carbon dioxide removal in central Europe: tensions between institutions, interests, and ideas hindering scaling up. *Climate policy*, pp.1–19. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2025.2478286> [Accessed June 21, 2025].
- Mosquera-Losada, M.R. et al., 2017. *How can policy support the uptake of agroforestry in Europe?*, Cranfield University. Available at: https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/files/pub/docs/deliverable_8_24_how_can_policy_support_agroforestry1.pdf.
- OKLIMA, 2025. Les haies, alliées de la transition écologique : comment réintégrer ces écosystèmes dans nos paysages agricoles ? *OKLIMA*. Available at: <https://www.oklima.fr/haies-dans-lagriculture-un-ecosysteme-restaurer/> [Accessed November 30, 2025].
- Paris, P. et al., 2016. Alley coppice : an evaluation of integrating short rotation coppice and timber trees. In *Proceedings of the IFASA Conference, Newport*. International Farming System Association. Boku: ifsa.boku.ac.at, pp. 1–9. Available at: https://ifsa.boku.ac.at/cms/fileadmin/IFSA2016/IFSA2016_WS32_Paris.pdf.
- PromHaies, 2015. L'Agroforesterie intraparcellaire - Associer production agricole et arbres sur la même parcelle. Available at: https://www.promhaies.net/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/plaquette_agroforesterie2015.pdf.
- ReSoil, 2025. Compensation carbone France : prix et tendances en 2025. *resoilag.com*. Available at: <https://www.resoilag.com/blog/ou-en-est-le-marche-volontaire-de-credits-carbone-en-france-en-2025> [Accessed November 24, 2025].
- RRAF, 2018. *Agroforesterie et Statut de Fermage*, Réseau Rural Agroforestier Français. Available at: <https://www.agroforesterie.fr/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/agroforesterie-et-statut-du-fermage.pdf>.
- Sanson, B., 2023. La BCAE8. *Réseau Haies*. Available at: <https://reseauhaies.fr/la-bcae8/> [Accessed August 22, 2025].

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